

URBANOME

Urban Observatory for Multi-participatory Enhancement of
Health and Wellbeing

WORK PACKAGE 2: Urban Living Labs for participatory
planning and pilot interventions

D2.1. Good Practice guidelines for setting up and managing Urban Living Labs

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List of Acronyms

API	Application Programming Interface
AU	Aarhus University
AUTH	Aristotle University of Thessaloniki
CSI	City Science Initiative
DDoS	Distributed Denial of Service
DNA	Deoxyribonucleic acid
DPO	Data Protection Officer
ENoLL	European Network of Living Labs
EU	European Union
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulations
GWAS	Genome-wide association study
H2020	Horizon 2020
ICT	Information and Communications Technology
IF	Incidental findings
IT	Information Technology
IUSS	University School for Advanced Studies Pavia
KWMC	Knowle West Media Centre
LL	Living Lab
MD	Medicine Doctor
NBS	Nature-based solutions
NGO	Non-governmental organisation
OECD	Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development
PPPP	Public Private People Partnership
PSO	Public Sector Organisation
RGU	Robert Gordon University
RNA	Ribonucleic acid
RRI	Responsible Research and Innovation
SMEs	Small and medium-sized enterprises
TLS	Transport layer security
UNDESA	United Nations Department of Economic and Social Affairs
UN-HABITAT	United Nations Human Settlement Programme
ULL	Urban Living Lab
WP	Work Package

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Executive summary

The aim of this deliverable is to present guidelines and best practices for Urban Living Labs (ULLs). The deliverable focuses on the operational and organisational perspective of ULLs, as well as the engagement of the quadruple helix stakeholders and the co-creative activities. The deliverable offers an overview of the key characteristics of the ULLs based on the extensive literature review, followed by practical information on how to set-up an ULL following a mapping canvas approach. The first part of the deliverable, strongly emphasises relevant aspects related to governance models, roles within ULLs, and business models. The second part of the deliverable focuses on the co-design and co-creative activities, and presents practical tools and methodologies that will guide ULL practitioners through co-creation processes. Furthermore, the deliverable highlights key aspects related to data protection issues. The final part of the deliverable presents good practices from URBANOME ULLs and other successful European funded projects. The research results presented in this deliverable are a valuable source of knowledge not only for URBANOME project partners, but for anyone willing to create and maintain a sustainable ULL. The set of guidelines provided by this is applicable in different contexts.

1. Introduction

1.1. Purpose and target group

The aim of this deliverable is to present guidelines and best practices for ULLs, from an organizational point of view, as well as how the ULL co-creative activities should be efficiently managed. In addition, the deliverable provides tangible tools and practical information throughout the ULL mapping canvas, business model development guidelines, data protection guidelines for user trials, as well as good practices from the URBANOME ULLs and other EC funded projects. The primary audience of this deliverable is constituted by the URBANOME partners, and in particular the organisations hosting the ULLs. In addition, the deliverable can be a useful document for all organisations interested in either developing or running ULL operations, and can be used beyond the scope of the URBANOME project.

1.2. Relation to other activities

This deliverable is the output of “Task 2.1 Definition of Good Practices for setting up and managing Urban Living Labs”, which has collected pre-existing experiences, best practices and guidelines for the ULLs. Through the deliverable, the URBANOME ULLs are guided through various stages of ULL development and the quadruple helix engagement with the aim to enhance citizens participation in European cities and to co-develop sustainable and healthy lifestyles.

This deliverable serves as a baseline for all activities of the ULLs and is strongly connected to all work packages. In particular, the deliverable feeds “Task 2.2 Co-creation processes and pathways towards participatory planning & citizen empowerment” and it is strongly linked with “D2.2 Report on the creation of the ULL and the concerning challenges to address”, as it outlines the data collection methodology through the mapping canvas that produces results which are then analysed in D2.2.

This deliverable is also strongly linked with “Task 2.3 on Physical and mental health and wellbeing and co-creative solutions workshops”, as the co-design and co-creative methodologies are presented in this document. In addition to the links within WP2, the deliverable feeds all the other work packages, where testing with the quadruple helix will be taking place, namely WP3, WP4 and WP5. The deliverable also feeds WP7 activities on ULL governance, and it is strongly linked with “Task 9.2 Training” through the business models and governance chapters”.

2. Key characteristics of Urban Living Labs

2.1. What is an Urban Living Lab?

ULLs have gained a central role in cities worldwide. There are many definitions of ULLs that highlight different characteristics of these pro-innovative ecosystems. In this section, the most relevant concepts and characteristics of ULLs are presented.

To clearly understand the basic components of an ULL, it is important to first gain a sound understanding of what the “Living Lab approach” is about, in a broader sense. Living Labs are defined as “*user-centred, open innovation ecosystems based on a systemic user co-creation approach in public-private-people partnerships, integrating research and innovation processes in real-life communities and settings*” (ENoLL, 2013). It needs to be highlighted that Living Labs are a specific type of open innovation networks that comprise diverse actors, resources, and activities (Dutilleul, Birrer, and Mensink 2010; Leminen and Westerlund 2016; Schaffers and Turkama 2012; Ståhlbröst and Lassinantti 2015). Living labs can offer a fruitful architecture for the deployment of open innovation through co-creation mechanisms and user involvement (Nyström et al. 2014). Living Labs play a multifaced role in society, in the context of building upon human capital, inspiring creativity, boosting multi-stakeholder collaboration, and contributing to the development of cities and regions where they operate. Living Labs are providers of a conducive environment where users and producers co-create in a trusted, open ecosystem that enables innovation (World Bank and European Network of Living Labs 2015).

Schuurman distinguished three different levels of analysis within the Living Lab phenomena (Schuurman 2015):

- The macro or organisational level.
- The meso or project level.
- The micro or user activity level.

Table 1 presents the Living Lab three-layer model and its key components.

Table 1 Living Lab three-layer model

Level	Definition	Research paradigm
Macro or organisational level	Living Lab constellation consisting of organized stakeholders (PPP-partnership)	Open Innovation: knowledge transfer between organizations
Meso or project level	Living Lab innovation project	Open & User Innovation: real-life experimentation, active user involvement, multi-method and multi-stakeholder
Micro or user activity level	Living Lab methodology consisting of different research steps	User Innovation: user involvement & contribution for innovation

Source: Schuurman, 2015.

According to Westerlund, Leminen and Rajahonka, research approaches that focus on Living Labs can be divided into seven broad categories: (i) Design, (ii) Ecosystem, (iii) City, (iv) University, (v) Innovation, (vi) User, (vii) Living Lab. Each of these broad topics includes a set of subcategories. Under the third category, “City”, three additional dimensions can be distinguished: Urban Living Labs, cities as collaborative innovation platforms, and smart city development (Westerlund, Leminen, and Rajahonka 2018).

What is also worth-mentioning is that research on Living Labs is moving from a conceptual focus to more practical implications, on how to manage Living Labs, their stakeholders and different processes in novel application areas such as the urban city context (Westerlund et al. 2018).

ULLs can be considered both as an arena (geography bounded space) and as an approach for intended collaboration among all quadruple helix actors that aim at fostering innovations in the urban ecosystem (Schuurman and Leminen 2021).

One of the most basic definitions states that *“an Urban Living Lab is a Living Lab formed in an urban area, including different stakeholders such as companies, researchers, authorities, users, and residents who develop solutions for existing problems in an urban area”* (Engez, Leminen, and Aarikka-Stenroos 2021). Urban Living Labs can be considered as *“early experimentation gardens”* in which residents, private actors, governments, and knowledge institutions interact in real time to design, test, and fine-tune social and technical interventions. These *“early experimentation gardens”* are embedded in the city neighbourhoods and provide learning arena for co-creation of new ideas (Ahmad 2020). In addition to that, Nesti points out that *“Urban Living Labs are public spaces where local authorities engage citizens to develop innovative urban services. Their strength and popularity stem from a methodology based on open innovation, experimentation, and citizen engagement”* (Nesti 2018).

According to Concilio, ULLs have three main potentials: (i) Urban Living Labs are practice-based environments that (ii) can create cross-boundary arenas in which diverse actors can interact, and (iii) ULLs are contexts for new modes of urban activism (Concilio 2016).

The ULL approach on the one hand requires substantial efforts in organisation, but on the other hand facilitates the processes of data sharing and collection, integrates expertise from different research fields, and provides tools for testing and evaluation (Steen and van Bueren 2017c). ULLs can have different thematic domains, e.g. health and wellbeing, agriculture, culture and creativity, energy and environment, circular economy, smart cities, etc.

ULLs have a crucial role in inspiring and maintaining collaboration among actors representing different spheres of socio-economic life. The specific functioning of Living Labs is based on the multi-stakeholder collaboration in a real-life context with extensive usage of different co-creation and experimentation methodologies. ULLs lay upon the (Evans et al. 2019):

- **Multi-method approach** – different ULLs adapt different co-creation methodologies to their needs. There is no “golden rule” that fits all purposes. Each ULL is different and needs a tailored set of tools and methodologies. In this handbook, a broad set of successful methods and examples of their application have been provided.
- **User engagement** – a key to the success of any ULL is active engagement of users already at the beginning of the process. Users play an active role in ULL activities as co-innovators.
- **Multi-stakeholder participation** – it is critically important to involve all relevant stakeholders in the ULL activities. The engaged stakeholders must represent all quadruple helix actors: public sector, business, academia, and people. A more detailed description of the quadruple helix involvement has been provided in section 2.3.
- **ULL real-life setting** – is another key characteristic of ULLs. Collaboration among all quadruple helix actors takes place in real-life context. It can be either a physical or virtual space of interactions to achieve the desired outcomes.
- **Co-creation** – successful ULLs follow a bottom-up approach in which users are co-creators in the innovation process. A more detailed description of the co-creation in the ULL context with examples of successful tools and methodologies has been provided in chapter 4.

Figure 1 Key elements of Urban Living Labs

Source: Living Lab Methodology Handbook, U4IoT.

Figure 1 presents the key elements that ULLs lay upon. A successful ULL must satisfy all the above-mentioned components to be sustainable in the long-term. However, research shows that there are many initiatives labelled as “Living Labs” that do not include one or more key components that constitute a “true” Living Lab (Steen and van Bueren 2017a). Also, maintaining a successful transdisciplinary collaboration is a highly challenging task (Kalinauskaite et al. 2021).

2.2. Key components and domains of Urban Living Labs

The ULL concept can be defined and understood in many different ways. What makes the analysis of ULLs even more challenging and interesting, is the richness of thematic domains that ULLs may address (e.g. health and wellbeing, energy, environment, nature-based solutions, culture and creativity, etc.). Although ULLs are extremely complex, a clear understanding of key components that constitute these pro-innovative ecosystems provides a sound basis for setting up and managing a sustainable ULL (Chroneer, Stahlbrost, and Habibipour 2019).

The UNaLAB (<https://unalab.eu/>) research team proposed an approach that distinguishes seven critical components of ULLs. This approach is applicable to ULLs addressing different thematic areas (see Figure 2). Each of the following components requires careful consideration to ensure a success of an ULL in the long run (UNaLAB 2019):

- **The governance and management structure** – is a complex set of activities that are critical for ensuring the long-term success of an Urban Living Lab. They focus on the way in which an Urban

Living Lab is organised and managed both on the strategic and operational levels. All activities must be supported by the city decision-makers, local governments, and politicians.

- **Financing and business model** – a sustainable business model creates, delivers and captures value for all ULL stakeholders. A business model must be well thought out and clearly defined to guarantee the sustainability of an Urban Living Lab over the duration of a project.
- **Urban context** – it is another level of considerations while setting up an Urban Living Lab. The urban context is the setting in which Urban Living Lab activities will be organised. It can be either a street, district or the whole city. Key aspects that need to be considered in relation to the urban setting are, for instance: place and its ownership, physical and technical infrastructure, future plans, responsibility.
- **Innovation domain** – Urban Living Labs can have different thematic domains, e.g. health and wellbeing, energy, environment, nature-based solutions, culture and creativity, etc. It is of vital importance to understand the focus of an Urban Living Lab and clarify what value will be co-created and for whom.
- **Partners and users** – correspond to the quadruple helix model of engagement and the necessity to invite different stakeholders representing academia, public sector, private sector and citizens. It is worth noticing that partners can have different roles, for instance: innovator, experimenter, tester, lead participant or just a passive role. When it comes to the engagement of key stakeholders – it is critical to consider their objectives to contribute, motivations, level of engagement, types of activities and membership model.
- **The approach and methods** – there are various tools and methods for data collection and analysis in an Urban Living Lab context. The most successful tools are presented in the later chapters of this handbook. There is no golden formula for a set of tools and methods that could be a perfect solution for all Urban Living Labs. Each ULL is unique and requires a tailored combination of tools and methods. While choosing the most appropriate tools and methodologies, several additional aspects must be taken into account: sustainability, inclusiveness, openness, responsibility, and value-creating.
- **The ICT infrastructure** – The importance of ICT infrastructure has become even higher due to the COVID-19 pandemic. ICT infrastructure supports all Urban Living Lab activities. These are both existing and desirable ICT tools and solutions.

The approach proposed by the UNaLAB team has common points with research conducted by other scholars. For instance, Hossain, Leminen and Westerlund, based on systemic literature review of a sample of 114 research papers, identified the following characteristics of Urban Living Labs: (i) Real-life environments (context); (ii) Stakeholders' participation; (iii) Activities' oriented; (iv) Focus on business models and networks; (v) Methods, tools and approaches; (vi) Addressing challenges; and (vii) Producing outcomes (Hossain, Leminen, and Westerlund 2019).

Figure 2 Key Characteristics of Urban Living Labs

Source: Living Lab Handbook for Urban Living Labs Developing Nature-Based Solutions (UNaLAB 2019).

2.3. Quadruple helix innovation model – essentials

Since the multi-stakeholder collaboration based on quadruple helix model is at the heart of all ULL activities, it is critical to clearly understand the key characteristics of this model. This section provides the reader with an explanation of the essentials of the quadruple helix model. Finally, it equips the reader with a set of advice on how to manage interactions between entities, within the quadruple helix.

Living Labs encompass societal and technological dimensions simultaneously in a collaborative approach as a “quadruple helix structure” including citizens, industry, knowledge institutions and municipalities (see for “Living Lab definitions” (Compagnucci et al. 2021). The Quadruple Helix builds off the Triple Helix structure, which describes the ideal environment for innovation as an essentially networked environment structured around collaboration between actors from industry, government, and university (Etzkowitz and Leydesdorff 1995). Operating in the triple helix, universities spur on innovation by conducting and communicating path breaking research, which industry builds on when it engages in strategic partnerships to bring new goods and services to market, and PSOs formulate policies, which support and promote knowledge and value generating activities by both sectors.

The Quadruple Helix extends the Triple Helix by accounting for the key role played by citizens in the innovation process (Borghys et al. 2020). By including citizens, it is possible to ensure that innovations are sufficiently accessible, align with core societal values, and reflect the interests of the public.

This model was expanded even further to demonstrate how four components of the quadruple helix are involved in complex, multi-layered, dynamic and bi-directional interactions (Schütz, Heidingsfelder, and Schraudner 2019). When establishing the connections with the core stakeholders, the ULL managers need to navigate the complex and multi-faceted interactions between the stakeholders in order to ensure their active involvement in innovation projects (see Figure 3). Bringing the quadruple helix actors together is a challenging task and requires many efforts from everyone engaged in this process. In the later parts of this deliverable practical guidelines on how to interact with stakeholders have been provided.

Figure 3 The Quadruple Helix Model adapted by Fraunhofer (2016), originally developed by Carayannis and Campbell (2009).

In the first place, it is of vital importance to understand why these stakeholders should be brought together. In particular, it should be understood why citizens should be included in the co-design process, as they are the group that can be most challenging to reach out to and engage. The study by Värmland County Administrative Board has shown that lack of involvement of citizens might lead to (Värmland County Administrative Board 2018):

- Products and services not being used.
- Lack of transparency.
- Innovators and end-users not understanding each other.
- Frustration and production of a technical innovation instead of social.

The analysis of regional innovation strategies shows that while the cooperation of the academia and the industry through science parks is prevalent, there is a lack of policies and strategies where the quadruple and even triple helix models are applied (Cavallini et al. 2016).

Managing the relationships within the quadruple helix – citizens perspective

Why involve the civil society?

Overall, the greatest risk of disengagement of the civil society is that the products and services that are provided will not be used by the citizens and will consequently fail. When products, services or city re-designs are developed through the involvement of the quadruple helix, there is a greater chance that user-friendly solutions will be taken up by the population. In addition, this method strengthens the empowerment of the citizens who will feel more connected to the product or a solution, and thus will consequently increase trust towards the innovators (Värmland County Administrative Board 2018). Next to that, the citizens will more likely become further involved in the innovation system.

An often overlooked aspect of the citizen engagement is ensuring representation of views from different groups of citizens. Therefore, the ULL should strive to reach out to different layers of the society and engage people from different age, gender, ethnic, religious and socio-economic groups. Engagement activities should be adapted according to the audience, taking into consideration for example work schedules, child duties, linguistic barriers and other factors that might discourage citizens from participating. More information on various aspects related to inclusiveness is included in section 4.5. One of the instances how the participation could be expanded to include multifaced civil society is through the accessibility and availability of the internet (Cavallini et al. 2016).

The ULL needs to attract the citizens' attention through effective communications campaigns and prepare workshop sessions that have an appealing design in order to avoid participation drop-off.

Trust and relationship building

The trust built with the quadruple helix can be broken if not properly managed. In the case of the citizens, they can feel disillusioned with the Living Lab approach if they see their voice is not heard or are disappointed that their idea is not implemented. It is therefore imperative that the ULL ensures there is adequate information flow between the different levels of the quadruple helix. For instance, the participants in co-design workshops need to be aware of the process and possible outcomes. It also needs to be clear that while every input is welcome, due to technical, budgetary or other issues not all ideas might be feasible and implemented. The citizens should also not feel discouraged when submitting their ideas and should be aware of the proper follow-up from the project owner. If a false perception on the work done by the ULL is given, citizens might be discouraged from expressing their opinions in further projects.

Schütz et. al point out that it is not sufficient to announce to the participants that their perspective is being heard and will in some abstract way influence future decisions. Instead, ULL professionals who are running the interactive workshops with the citizens need to explain how the citizens perspective will be transferred to the experts (academia) and decision makers (public officials) and how the final solution will be developed with the private sector. The citizens need to understand to what extend their participation will have an impact on the solution or final product (Schütz et al. 2019).

Appropriate language

The ULL needs to make sure that the language used is common and well terms and definitions are well understood by all groups of the quadruple helix. In that regard, academics need to increase their efforts to communicate their research results to non-experts. When participatory workshops include different representatives of the quadruple helix, the workshop facilitator needs to ensure sufficient time is kept for discussion between the participants in order to developer their views further and understand perspectives of each of the groups (Schütz et al. 2019).

2.4. Urban challenges and the value of ULLs

Today, almost half of the world's population live in cities and this share is projected to increase to 70% by 2050 (OECD and European Commission 2020). The United Nations Department of Economic and Social Affairs published population figures for rural and urban areas from 1950 up to 2100. These figures present a distinctly faster increase in the urban population, the urban population quadrupling between 1975 and 2050 (UNDESA 2019). Cities are continuously growing because they are centers of various economic activities and offer their dwellers opportunities for living a better life (OECD 2015). Moreover, cities account for more than 80 % of global GDP and are essential for jobs' generation (UN-HABITAT 2020).

Urban areas are hubs of innovation and productivity and at the same time goods and services providers to the regions, they are located in and key contributors to national social, economic, and environmental performance (OECD 2015). Cities are also key players to achieve Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) (OECD 2014, 2020a) and at the same are at the forefront of technological transformation of contemporary economies and societies (UN-Habitat 2020a).

Metropolitan areas are key to creating jobs, generating income and facilitating economic growth. It should be also emphasised that it is the creativity of individuals and their collective actions within metropolitan areas that are the driving force for finding innovative solutions that foster the growth and success of those areas (Stolarick and Florida 2006).

As pointed out by Charles Landry, the author of the "Creative City" concept: *"Cities have one crucial resource – their people. Human cleverness, desires, motivations, imagination and creativity are replacing location, natural resources and market access as urban resources. The creativity of those who live in and run cities will determine future success. Of course, this has always been critical to cities' ability to survive and adapt. As cities became large and complex enough to present problems of urban management, so they became laboratories that developed the solutions – technological, conceptual and social – to the problems of growth"* (Landry 2008).

Cities and urban areas are in state of constant flux, with systemic change and transformation occurring on many fronts. ULLs have emerged as a new type of intervention format for leveraging sustainable urban change (Voytenko et al. 2016). ULLs have a great potential to contribute to the sustainable development of metropolitan areas as well as to support health & wellbeing of citizens. The application of the Living Lab concept in the urban ecosystem enables rapid social, economic and technological transformation. In this sense, city districts can be considered as innovation spaces in which new applications are tested on a large scale (Engez et al. 2021).

ULLs reflect a form of experimental governance that encourages urban stakeholders to test and develop new products, services, technologies, and ways of living. These activities aim at producing innovative solutions that support combating challenges related to sustainability, resilience, and climate change (Fuenfschilling, Frantzeskaki, and Coenen 2019; Voytenko et al. 2016).

ULLs are vehicles for collaborative city planning, places of experimental learning, and learning environments for new forms of governance (Scholl and Kemp 2016). Another relevant feature of ULLs is their ability to serve as a practice-based approach for participatory city design (Blomkamp 2021).

What is also worth-mentioning, ULLs have potential to solve complex societal problems that require multidisciplinary knowledge. In ULLs, stakeholders representing different spheres of socio-economic life and various knowledge domains, work together to co-create value for society.

According to the White Paper on Citizen Science for Europe, our society requires a new contract between all actors to be able to address global challenges. Only collaboration between different policy stakeholders can ensure the implementation of adequate measures and drive long run and sustainable transformation. ULLs may serve as an interaction channel between society, scientists, and policy makers (Socientize 2014).

ULLs are both an innovation policy tool and a way for achieving the SDGs (UN-Habitat 2020c, 2020b; UNDESA n.d.). ULLs can bring top down and bottom-up initiatives together and ensure that voices of all relevant groups are included. It has a critical role for creating mission-oriented innovations that aim at responding to real-life needs and challenges (Mazzucato 2018), and for strengthening collaboration among different interest groups (European Commission 2016, 2019).

Contemporary global trends in the area of innovation policy emphasize the necessity to develop solutions that correspond to specific local conditions and to put human needs in the center of interest of decision-makers, as well as ensuring the participation of citizens in creating the policy that determines the functioning of the regions in which they live (OECD 2020b; OECD and European Commission 2020). Citizen-science can be used as a valuable approach in the ULL context to enhance the policy-making participatory mechanisms (Veeckman and Temmerman 2021). Participatory policymaking gain popularity due to rising complexity of policy problems. Policymakers are searching for successful methods to engage with a wide range of stakeholders during policy development and implementation processes (Blomkamp 2021).

The approach of Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI) is also of key importance. This means that social actors (scientists, citizens, policy makers, business, third sector organizations, etc.) work together throughout the research and innovation process to better align both the process and its results with the values, needs and expectations of society (European Commission n.d.).

It should be also pointed out the importance of the experimental approach to creating innovation policy. Experimentation requires designing a policy portfolio to solve specific problems step by step, ongoing monitoring and evaluation of the achieved results and reacting as quickly as possible. This process is also associated with constant learning (also from mistakes made) and applying improvements (OECD and World Bank 2014). This approach perfectly corresponds to the specificities of functioning of ULLs and the role they play in society.

According to Tukiainen, Leminen and Westerlund (2015), cities may be consider as collaborative innovation platforms for: (i) Improving everyday activities and life conditions of citizens; (ii) Creative consumer experiments; (iii) Experimenting and implementing new technologies; and (iv) Creating and re-creating new economic opportunities (Tukiainen, Leminen, and Westerlund 2015). ULLs can play a leading role in fostering collaborative innovation in cities. Table 2 presents guidelines for various forms of collaborative innovation in cities (Tukiainen et al. 2015).

Table 2 Guidelines for various forms of collaborative innovation in the city ecosystem

Collaborative innovation in cities	Means to participate for collaborative innovation	Innovation outcomes
Improvement of everyday activities and life conditions	Support activities by offering tangible and intangible resources such as tools and knowledge rather than interfering or steering such activities. Citizens are committed to those activities for their own reasons.	Harvest the ideas and knowledge created by citizens and user communities in real-life contexts.
Creative consumer experiments	Support activities by offering tangible and intangible resources such as tools and knowledge, but be involved in the creative activities to learn activities as such but also from novel forms of collaborative activities.	Learn emerging needs and wishes of citizens and customers at the grassroots level, but also as a mechanism to learn novel forms of open collaboration.
Experimentation and implementation of new technologies	Support the experiments and implementations by offering context, knowledge, and tools.	Validation of new ideas and prototypes of novel technologies.
Creation or recreation of economic opportunities	Use city as platform for creating new ideas, where the plurality of stakeholders, knowledge and ideas smash. The city is a boundless source of ideas but also a collaboration method between and with systems and communities.	New business opportunities.

Source: Tukiainen et al., 2015.

Concluding, it needs to be highlighted that ULLs are an essential component of an urban ecosystem. Maintaining effective multistakeholder collaboration is now more important than ever. Successful ULL initiatives have an additional great potential to combat negative consequences of the COVID-19 pandemic and to build more sustainable, resilient, and equitable cities and societies.

3. Setting up an Urban Living Lab: tools and methods

The rising popularity of the ULL concept makes more and more people eager to better understand how to set up an ULL and how to make it sustainable in the long run. This chapter provides the reader with the knowledge needed to establish and maintain a successful ULL. Special emphasis is given on the relevance of governance and business models, as well as roles within ULLs. In the last section of the chapter, the mapping canvas is presented as dynamic tool that guides the activities of URBANOME ULLs. This tool can be successfully implemented to other ULLs from different thematic domains worldwide with slight adaptations.

3.1. Governance models for Urban Living Labs

The governance and management structure reflects on the way an ULL is managed and organised on the strategic or operational level (UNaLAB 2019). It is one of the seven key components that encompasses leadership, ownership and management questions. The governance model of ULLs defines its flexibility and effectiveness, as well as its long-term sustainability (Chroner et al. 2019).

Why should an ULL have a governance model?

- To ensure sustainability and viability.
- To gain insights into new ways of handling societal challenges.
- To communicate effectively.
- To avoid failure.
- To act in accordance with ethics, integrity, and a responsible code of conduct.
- To have a starting point that can indicate how an organization needs to improve.

Each Living Lab has its own governance model that reflects the complex relationships between stakeholders in their local environment. There are however common steps to be undertaken when defining the governance structure. These steps include defining the participants, contributors, decision-making system, communication strategy and rewards for the participants. As the governance model requires involvement of different stakeholders, their priorities need to be understood and for that reason it takes time and trust to develop it (Vilariño, Karatzas, and Valcarce 2018).

Figure 4 Steps taken to define a governance model

Source: Own elaboration based on the UNaLAB Handbook (UNaLAB 2019).

In the first step, the ULL needs to identify its central actors. This raises the question not only of the hosting entity, but also of the organisations involved in the decision-making process. The following questions should be answered when brainstorming about the first step: who owns the ULL and who is responsible for it?

In the second step, the available budget needs to be defined. It should be clear how the ULL will be financed for the specific project, but also beyond the initial funding. In this step, the question on how the ULL is financed, by whom and of any other potential income sources needs to be tackled. In section 3.3 business model development is further presented.

The third step includes the organizational structure of the ULL as well, as its strategy, day-by-day activities, definition of internal roles, etc. When defining the internal roles, competences of the staff need to be defined, as well as “Who makes decisions of go or no-go?”, “Who is working in the ULL?”, “Where does it reside in the organisation, which organisational belonging does it have?”.

The step on the communication strategy focuses both on internal and external communications. Here the flow of information within the organisation needs to be defined, as well as the crucial role of communicating with and towards the quadruple helix, as presented in the section 2.3.

And finally, the governance structure has to include the desired outcome, for each involved party. At that stage, a definition of the outcome of the ULL is needed drawing back to the Business Model strategy introduced in the first steps, but it should then be re-defined in the final stage of the governance development process.

3.2. Roles within Urban Living Labs

An ULL has both internal and external roles that are essential for its organisation and management. The external roles belong to the actors towards whose an ULL normally interacts with, while internal roles reflect on its organisational structure. Both sets of roles can be defined while setting up the governance structure with the difference that the internal roles are important for managing the ULL, while the external roles are relevant for setting up the ULL activities (UNaLAB 2019). Figure 5 presents the overview of internal and external roles within an ULL, whereas Table 3 guides the reader through the description of the key characteristics of each role.

Figure 5 Overview of the Internal and External roles of an ULL

Source: Own elaboration based on UNaLAB Handbook (UNaLAB 2019).

Table 3 Description of internal and external roles within the Urban Living Lab

INTERNAL ROLES		Role	Tasks
INTERNAL ROLES	ULL manager		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The most apparent internal role that needs to be defined - Manages everyday activities of the ULL - Develops ULL projects - Ensures that an ULL maintained effectively and sustainably - This person can cover more than one internal role
	Human interaction specialist		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Supports an ULL processes - Perform user-centred interactions - Analyses the results from different human interaction methods - This person can be either employed by the ULL or engaged on the project level - Involved in various ULL activities (e.g. planning and innovation processes, designing concepts and principles, need-finding studies, testing and evaluation) - Responsible for testing solutions before their implementation in the real-life context
	Pilot manager		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Facilitates the implementation and test of the innovation - This person can be either employed by the ULL or engaged in a different way - Involved in various ULL activities (e.g. planning, coordinating and implementing real world experimentation) - Coordinates interactions between the other roles (e.g. innovators, users, problem owners, and project manager)
	Panel manager		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Responsible for recruiting and interacting with a panel of stakeholders involved in testing and evaluation activities - Decides which users need to be involved in the process - Collaborates closely with the human interaction specialist (e.g. while interacting with the engaged stakeholders) - Involved in various ULL activities (e.g. pre-studies and need-finding, test and evaluation) - Distributes information about experimental pilots externally and supports the pilots - Communicates with the stakeholders and coordinates communication among them
	Project manager		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Manages the city development project as a whole - This person can be either employed by the city, ULL or engaged on the project level - Often decides on potential actors to engage in a project
EXTERNAL ROLES		Role	Tasks
EXTERNAL ROLES	Innovator		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Develops wide range of innovations (based on the thematic focus of the ULL) - This person can be either employed by the city, a SME, a large company, a NGO or a citizen - Contributes to the final design of the innovation
	User		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - This role can be covered either by employees at the municipality, citizens or those using the final solution - Can be engaged in all ULL processed - Supports the ULL with evaluation of ideas, concepts, prototypes and final solutions - Shares feedback on needs, values and related to a specific solution/situation
	Affectee		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - This person is affected by the solutions developed by the ULL and implemented in a real-life context - This person is not employed at the ULL - Not involved in using or purchasing the solution developed by the ULL - ULLs provide ways to strengthen the influence of affectees and make their voices heard
	Problem owner		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Contributes to unleashing a need/problem to solve - Shares knowledge on identified need/problem

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Supports the solution finding processes at the ULL - It can be for instance the city owning concrete problems/challenges to solve
	Financer	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - An organisation that provides funding (for example, in URBANOME project the European Commission is the financer) - Has the power what is done at ULL and how and become a gatekeeper - Influences ULL actors' decisions and actions
	Context provider	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Involved in implementation of ULL activities - Has relationship dependencies with the ULL - In URBANOME project, context providers are the partner cities in which the ULLs operate

Source: Adopted from the UNaLab Handbook (UNaLAB 2019).

As it is shown in Figure 5, the internal roles are: (1) ULL manager; (2) Human interaction specialist; (3) Pilot manager; (4) Panel Manager; and (5) Project Manager. Whereas the external roles are as follows: (1) Innovator, (2) User; (3) Affectee; (4) Problem owner; (5) Financer; and (6) Context provider. In table 3, descriptions of all roles, emphasizing the key responsibilities of each of them, have been provided. What is also worth noticing, is that all roles, both internal and external, are strongly interconnected and rely on each other. Figure 6 explains different interactions between the roles. Internal roles are indicated in green and external ones – in blue.

While setting up an ULL, it is critical to first carefully consider the internal roles and make sure that human resources needed to maintain the day-to-day activities will be available. Also, a clear division of tasks and responsibilities of different ULL team members needs to be discussed and agreed at the very beginning. That will allow to ensure that all relevant ULL activities are appropriately managed, and there are no mismatches with the actual needs.

Once all relevant internal roles are in place, it is of vital importance to decide how to interact with the external environment. As it is visualised in Figure 6, there are different connections between internal and external roles that are determined by the scope of activities of different role holders. For instance, ULL manager, since it is the most apparent person that ensures that an ULL is maintained effectively and sustainably (who is at the same time responsible for a big variety of activities), interacts with: (1) Innovator, while developing various innovations; (2) Context provider, while implementing ULL activities in the specific real-life context; (3) Financer, while discussing the strategic decisions and financial matters; and (4) Problem owner, while unleashing the problem to solve. In comparison, the Panel manager, who is heavily engaged in recruiting and interacting with the panel of stakeholders while testing and evaluation activities, interacts mostly with Users and Affectees. Similar interconnections can be found while exploring the links between the other roles.

What also needs to be highlighted, is that even though all internal roles do not interact with all external roles, there are close connections between all ULL team members. Also, some internal roles interact with the same external roles. For instance, Pilot manager, Human interaction specialist and Panel manager closely collaborate with Citizens (both Users and Affectees). It means that their actions need to be aligned. That requires an effective flow of information between all internal roles and constant knowledge exchange among them.

To conclude considerations included in this part of the deliverable, it needs to be highlighted that all ULL roles need to be well-thought at the very early stages of setting up an ULL. Also, an excellent coordination between all internal roles is essential for ensuring that different ULL processes will be

managed effectively. Careful planning and effective dialogue with all relevant parties are key in developing a sustainable ULL.

Figure 6 Interaction between internal and external ULL roles

Source: UNaLab Urban Living Lab Playground game board (developed by ENOLL).

3.3. Business models for Urban Living Labs

Business model is a term used to define a company or organisation’s plan for making a profit. The plan typically identifies the products or services that the company aims to sell in addition to defining its target market, consumers as well as related expenses in producing said products or services (Kopp 2020). Overall, business models are designed to help companies in attracting investments whilst navigating internal managerial structures.

Living Labs are organisations structured differently than companies. As is the case of URBANOME ULLs, as well as in majority of the Living Labs in Europe, reliance on public grants and subsidy programs is prevalent (Katzky 2012). Katzky also points out that creating Living Labs generating the largest revenue from private markets is the biggest challenge. Therefore, to create an economically viable Living Lab, internal processes of the organisations need to be aligned with the needs of external stakeholders.

In this section, we present alternative activities to income generation apart from public funding and introduce two models that URBANOME ULLs can use to define their value and products or services for market readiness.

Revenue generation through products or services

Living Labs can generate revenues by providing user validation services to other businesses. Revenues in this service are similar to consulting fees, where service is charged on per-hour basis or a fixed price for a project completion. This type of service allows for quick revenue generation, however, under the condition that the Living Lab is able to find new clients and continuously provide this type of service. An alternative creation of revenue proposed by Katzy (2012) involves marketing a product or a service (Katzy 2012). This type of revenue generation is riskier since the Urban Living Lab would need to bear the cost until the project breaks even. However, with successful projects, the ULL could become a supplier of products and services and turn into a company-like organisation. The next revenue generating option involves cooperation and investment from business angels, investors or venture capitalists to whom the Living Lab would hand over a project once it reached a certain level of maturity. This revenue generation option is beneficial for Urban Living Labs since their operations can be financially supported before the product reaches a market readiness level. However, in order to raise the attention and further investments, the ULL needs to structure the project in a way that shows its profitability and a clear value of its approach to the creation of new products or services.

Value creation

To achieve financial independence and attract revenues from different investors, the ULL should start its business model journey by defining its value and how it can be created. In fact, Richardson points out that common elements of business models include, value proposition, value creation and delivery system as well as the value capture model (Richardson 2008). Traditionally, companies focused on creating value by selling a product or a service have focused on improving their competitive advantage by adjusting the price, quality, distribution time, as well as other factors. However, Degnegaard (2017), observes a change in this way of working and emphasizes that the experience of users, clients, patients or citizens has become a focal point in value creation (Degnegaard 2017). An additional layer to the value creation of business models was added, since organisations need to consider the larger societal purpose, a challenge and an opportunity. In this regard, a solution to a societal problem should be co-created with other stakeholders in the society, which a Urban Living Lab should have access to (ibidem).

How to create value propositions?

Living Labs should therefore aim to develop sustainable business models that focus on value creation for the society and their customers which leads to sustainable development of the society, as well as the organisation (Lüdeke- Freund 2010). To re-think the value proposition of the ULLs, and to reconfigure the network of stakeholders that are involved in creating, delivering and receiving its value, we propose the use of the *Value Mapping Tool* shown in Figure 7. The tool helps organisations in creating value propositions, which support the definition of sustainable business models.

Figure 7 Value creation tool

Source: Short et al. 2013.

The tool performs three actions; first, it systemically assesses the value (it is about generating new value and reflecting on aspects that could be either missed or destroyed); secondly, it approaches value from a network perspective instead of organisation's centric view of the value; and thirdly it provides a multi-stakeholder view of the value (Short et al. 2013). The potential of the tool is maximised if each stakeholder identified participates in the activity.

How to use the tool?

The exercise begins in the centre of the circle, working outwards. The first step is to define the product or service that will be analysed. This could also be extended to a portfolio or products and services. Next, stakeholders are identified and placed on each section of the tool. Some areas can also be left blank at the beginning of the exercise and added later when a new stakeholder is identified. The exercise concludes with a brainstorming activity where each stakeholder section is populated based on the type of value it creates.

Living Labs as-a-service

The next tool developed by "imec" (Schuurman et al. 2019) draws its inspiration from the business model canvas while taking into consideration practical and unique experiences Living Lab face when

developing their business plans. The model called “Innovatrix” consists of eight key elements. These elements include customer segment, needs, current practices, value proposition, solution, key partners, value capture and barriers. The Innovatrix tool, shown in Figure 8, is used to help Living Labs scope their user involvement activities while allowing them to iterate their business model (Schuurman et al. 2019).

Figure 8 Innovatrix model. Copyright: imec

Source: Schuurman et al. 2019.

How to use the tool?

- In the customer segment, the current state of the activities is drawn. The first column is used to map similarities between the three customer segments which are identified in the grey area. The following questions need to be asked: What customer segments should be focused on? What are their key characteristics and use context?
- The second segment focuses on the current needs. Customer needs are identified with a discussion on how these should be prioritized.
- The segment on current practices encompasses a market study. The Living Lab should map out the competitors, alternatives to their product/service offering and identify pains and gains of current practices.
- In the value proposition segment both current and future state of the value are mapped. It needs to be discussed what measurable impact exists or will be created for the customer segment.
- For the solution segment, the components of the solution and how these differ for different customer segments should be discussed.

- Value capture segment is used to discuss monetary and non-monetary value and what price should be set.
- Next, key partners are identified and it should be decided how the Living Lab will interact with its stakeholders.
- In the final segment on barriers, the Living Labs needs to play the devil’s advocate and define barriers to adoption, usage and market entry.

The workshop of mapping the Innovatrix model is normally conducted by a skilled facilitator. Two types of post-its are added to the model, depending on the assumptions they are referring to – yellow for assumptions and green for validated assumptions. Afterwards the “key uncertainties” are drawn by marking the most important assumptions. On the other hand, an analysis should be done on key uncertainties (Schuurman et al. 2019).

3.4. URBANOME ULL mapping canvas

The Living Lab Mapping Canvas is a tool developed within the URBANOME project for the purposes of outlining key components of the ULLs and understanding the state of the maturity of the URBANOME Urban Living Labs (see Figure 9). There are 14 different quadrants that guide each ULL team in identifying essential components and successful operations.

Figure 9 URBANOME ULL Mapping Canvas

Source: Approach developed by ENoLL for URBANOME ULLs purposes.

- The canvas mapping activity begins in the centre of the canvas by defining the **purpose** of the ULL and answering the question “why are we doing what we are doing in the first place?”.

- Next, the **vision and scope** of the ULL are identified. Scope refers to the “extent of the area or subject matter that something deals with or to which it is relevant” while in defining the vision, objectives to achieve in the long run should be described.
- In the **host organisation** quadrant, the Urban Living Lab needs to put down the name and type of the organisation hosting it. It can be a municipality, a research institute, a University or a private company. In the context of the URBANOME project the host organisation is the one receiving the funds for the Urban Living Lab activity.
- The ULL presents a superficial overview of the **quadruple helix stakeholders** it is already in touch with or has identified for its operations. In section 2.3 more information is provided on the quadruple helix and why it is imperative these stakeholders are included in the co-creation process.
- Next, the **internal roles** of the ULL should be defined. In this quadrant all of the staff working on the ULL activities within the URBANOME project are listed. In the two quadrants below the internal roles, the personnel should identify their strengths and assets, namely “what are the skills we have in the team that will help us achieve our goals? What are interpersonal/soft skills that we have? What are we good at, individually and as a team?”. The staff is also asked to identify their challenges and weaknesses they face individually and as a team and answer the questions “what our teammates should know about us? What are some obstacles we see ahead us that we are likely to face?” These two quadrants help us define any potential drawbacks that the ULL staff might face and whether these can be solved by providing training.
- In the farther left quadrant the personnel should be classified under the five internal roles as described in chapter 3.2. During the initial exercise with the mapping canvas, this classification might be difficult for the ULLs as internal roles are not clearly shaped. It is also possible that one person has more than one role and oversees different activities. Overall, we aim to understand the division of the personnel on the operational level and the stakeholder engagement activities.
- On the right hand side of the mapping canvas the operational matters of the ULL are reviewed. To understand the area in which the Urban Living Lab will operate, the **urban context** needs to be defined. This is where the solutions will be tested or implemented. It can be a street, district or the city as a whole. In relation to the urban context, place, ownership, physical infrastructure, technical infrastructure, future plans, responsibility and other activities must be taken into account.
- Reflecting on the internal operations is the **governance structure**. The governance and management structure reflects on the way that an ULL in the strategic or operational level is managed and organized. More information on the governance can be found in chapter 3.1.
- In addition to the governance structure a quadrant on the **business model** of the ULL is added to understand whether plans to support long-term commitment have been identified. This quadrant can provide relevant information on the longevity of the operations of the ULL. In chapter 3.3 two approaches outlining how the business model can be drafted are presented.
- In the far right corner the **approach and methods** already used by the ULL should be described. These refer to either data collection and data analysis methods as well as the engagement methods and tools. The ULL is asked to elaborate further on their existing experience with co-creation and the methods they are already familiar with.
- Next, the **communication channels** of the ULL should be identified, namely how the outreach to the participants is done, whether the ULL is communicating its activities to the external

stakeholders. Coherent communication is needed to ensure continuous engagement and trust of stakeholders.

- And finally, in the quadrant on **needs and expectations** the ULL identifies any points of improvement with regards to its operations and management. This quadrant helps us identify any issues or concerns that should be addressed in the URBANOME project.

4. Co-creation processes in Urban Living Labs

4.1. Urban Living Lab integrative process

In chapter 2, the key characteristics of ULLs have been presented. What needs to be highlighted also here, is that ULLs aim at solving wicked problems that are very complex, specific, and multicausal. Wicked problems are often social, economic or cultural, for instance those related to poverty, climate change, sustainability, education, etc. What makes them even more difficult to address, is the fact that they are intertwined with one another. Most of the urban problems are wicked by nature, meaning that it is impossible to find easy or quick solutions to these essentially unique challenges.

Finding valuable solutions to wicked problems requires special efforts and multi-stakeholder collaboration. Successful Urban Living Labs have the potential to tackle wicked problems. ULLs can offer a rich set of human-centric tools and methodologies that are crucial for developing solutions to wicked problems. What has been also mentioned in chapter 2, each ULL is unique and rooted in a specific context, so it requires a tailored approach while designing all ULL processes and activities.

Although each ULL is different and there is no “one size fits all solution”, perfectly applicable to all ULLs there are some approaches that can guide ULL practitioners through creating and developing a sustainable ULL.

An interesting example of such approach is ULL integrative process developed by Joelle Mastelic and Fiona Zimmerman from HES-SO Living Labs (Mastelic 2019) (see Figure 10). This approach is based on design thinking methodology and specifies necessary steps for generating citizen-centric innovations in the city ecosystem. The ULL integrative process is the approach that can structure the way in which each ULL project is organised. The following steps and their application under case-specific circumstances should be carefully considered.

Figure 10 The Urban Living Lab integrative process

Source: Model adopted from Mastelic, 2019.

The different steps of the ULL integrative process are further described below.

Step 1 – Scoping and select a practice

- Observe, engage and empathize with people to understand the essence of the problem.
- Gain an emphatic understanding of the problem you are trying to solve.
- Study the available data on your ecosystem, scope and understand the context.
- Immerse yourself in the physical environment (city ecosystem) to gain deeper personal understanding of the problem and be able to better navigate the activities of your ULL project.
- Identify the practices of the actors that have a strong impact (positive or negative) on the ecosystem.

Step 2 – Stakeholder Integration: Who are the Actors in the Living Lab?

- The main question that should guide the co-design process is who are our target stakeholders?
- What are the needs of our stakeholders?
- It is critical to involve citizens and the final users already since day zero for co-creating value to the targeted stakeholders.

Step 3 – Define and uncover barriers

- During this stage, you connect all the information collected during previous stages to come up with the concrete and relevant problem to solve.
- The three main principles for impactful Urban Living Lab projects are: focus, differentiation, and coherence.
- To uncover barriers, interview the key players individually. Are your assumptions true? What are the barriers and levers of action of the actors in your ULL?

Step 4 – Ideate and create a co-design plan

- This phase provides materials for building prototypes and putting creative solutions in the hands of the users.
- Ideate to find solutions to a problem that you have identified in the previous stages.
- A common vision and shared goals enable creative exchanges and then co-design with the users.
- Think outside the box, inspire collaborative creativity of all engaged stakeholders and try to look for alternative ways of viewing the problem.

Steps 5 & 6 – Prototype and test

- In Design Thinking, prototyping is an interactive tool that allows different options to be explored, considering users' expectations.
- A prototype is something that can represent a product or experience before the final version is available. Prototypes can take on a variety of forms, from a minimum viable product to services or experiences.
- The prototype or innovation should be presented to the users as a solution, to change habits and develop new contexts.
- The testing stage considers the interaction and feedback from users to fine-tune solutions, in iterative cycles.
- The evaluation phase should facilitate the stakeholder re-engagement and co-creation of the evaluation process, benchmarking, indicators and monitoring, as well as impact analysis to inform scale up and replication decisions.

Steps 7 & 8 – Implement and scale up

- The actual system is proven in operational environment.
- Test the solution outside the initial scope and enlarge its scope.
- Replicate the solution in other settings.

The ULL integrative process is a framework for all ULL activities. It guides ULL practitioners, step by step, through all the necessary stages of developing a sustainable Urban Living Lab. The concrete examples of tools and methodologies that can be deployed at different stages of the integrative process have been presented in chapters 3 and 4. Whereas, in chapter 6, a set of best practices and lessons learnt from different ULLs across Europe are presented and can serve as an inspiration for everyone who is going to start and run a viable and sustainable ULL.

4.2. Co-design: the approach, value and challenges

The approach towards co-design

Co-design is the process of involving stakeholders, including residents, to share their views and work collectively to find resolutions to challenging issues (Blomkamp 2018). Co-design is grounded in participatory design approaches (Sanders and Stappers 2008).

Sanders et al. delineated co-design as “..collective creativity as it is applied across the whole span of a design process..” (Sanders and Stappers 2008).

The concept of co-design is based on the notion of a more inclusive approach to design, where individuals are involved at all stages of the process from inception through to implementation of ideas (Munthe-Kaas 2015). Indeed, “*co-creation*” is a key defining feature of ULLs (Steen and van Bueren 2017b). In the context of designing public space, highlights how the approach of connecting different stakeholders enables “*...active participation and commitment, regardless of the social, cultural or professional environment of the participants*” (Remesar 2021). This highlights a key aspect of the co-design approach and reaffirms the requirement to be inclusive and specifically to include vulnerable groups in co-design activities.

The value of co-design

Co-design has been praised as yielding greater creative thinking, facilitating alignment with user requirements, financial efficacies resulting from better responsiveness, nurturing collaboration and trust between various parties, enable deeper connections with less accessible participants, and achieves greater “buy-in” through transformation processes (Blomkamp 2018). Though the extent of the advantage depending on context can be contested (see Blomkamp, 2018).

Glackin and Dionisio highlight how engagement at a local level in urban plans can increase the “sense of belonging” and partnership working of the local population, and how this participation is essential in terms of embracement and administration of the plans throughout and beyond the project (Glackin and Dionisio 2015).

There are identified benefits to stakeholders that are a by-product of co-design approaches. Co-design workshops have been highlighted as having psychological benefits for participants (Corcorana, Marshalla, and Walsh 2018). Lam et al. express “Engaging people in a creative process could help them appreciate their skills, knowledge and creativity, and recognise themselves as assets” (Lam et al. 2017).

The challenges of co-design

While there are numerous recognised benefits of co-design, the delivery of such an approach is not without its challenges. For example, trying to establish a “common ground” where different stakeholders have differing specialities, with diverging interests, can be challenging (Kleinsmann and Valkenburg 2008).

Pirinen reviewed the “barriers and enablers” of co-design in relation to service delivery identifying twenty challenges and associated opportunities for overcoming such difficulties (see Figure 11) (Pirinen 2016).

In additional to institutional, social and cultural challenges, the practicalities of conducting co-design workshops can also be problematic. This issue is particularly topical in the context of the COVID-19 pandemic, where opportunities to meet face-to-face have been regulated. Davis et al. specifically discuss co-design workshops in the context of the pandemic and highlight opportunities for engagement that extend beyond face-to-face participation including digital workshops that provide benefits such as engagement with a greater reach of participants (Davis et al. 2021). However, the downsides of the lack of face-to-face interaction are also acknowledged.

Co-design is vital for developing trust with local people and stakeholders, drawing on their specific knowledge and to continually review and assist in meeting the requirements of specific population

groups. However, these outcomes are dependent on how well co-design is executed (Evans and Terrey 2016).

The next section reviews possible approaches to co-design workshop activities.

Figure 11 Barriers and Enables of co-design to services

Source: Pirinen, 2016.

Engagement in co-design workshops

Focused workshops should be organised to engage with key stakeholders and local (formal) decision makers in an ULL to develop potential interventions. There are a variety of practical activities that can be undertaken to engage with participants such as storytelling and craft activities (Cruickshank, Coupe, and Hennessy 2013; Kankainen et al. 2012). “Icebreakers” can also be a useful way of engaging with stakeholders (Corcorana et al. 2018).

In addition to the research methodology adopted, consideration should also be given to the construct/design of the space for the workshops. The physical setting should facilitate activities and enhance, rather than constrain, opportunities to harbour participation and collaboration across the group (Calvo and De Rosa 2017). Understanding the key stakeholders within the ULL is an important step in the process of organising the co-design workshops. The quadruple helix model, discussed in section 2.3., identifies the key sectors in which stakeholders should be identified including business, academia, local government and citizens (Compagnucci et al. 2021). It is also acknowledged that there will also be other categories of stakeholder that are important within the living labs such as policy makers and media.

Furthermore, the number of participant’s attending workshops is another element that should be considered. While it is important to identify the key stakeholders, it is also necessary to review the number of participants to include in the workshops that will facilitate and encourage inclusion of all stakeholders.

Guidelines for facilitators

This section highlights some key aspects from the literature and handbook’s that are important to adopt across the URBANOME Living Labs. Below, the key points to consider when conducting co-design activities:

Undertake a mapping of the key stakeholders within the living labs and participants for the workshops.

Review the physical set up of co-design workshops to support collaboration.

Build trust with participants.

Appraise and consider methodological approaches for gathering data.

Never underestimate the importance of regular communication with stakeholders.

Organise face-to-face or digital workshops depending on requirements and suitability.

Monitor the co-design approaches taken, including reflection of best practice.

Evaluate the facilitators’ role in the co-design activities.

It is critically important to have an effective co-design process in place. The outcomes of the co-design activities will determine the success of co-creation processes in the next stages of developing an ULL project. This section provides the reader with knowledge on the most relevant aspects related to co-design. In the next section, essentials on co-creation and stakeholder engagement are explained. Additionally, the next part of the deliverable presents a set of successful tools and methods that can be a valuable source of inspiration for all ULL practitioners while developing the co-creation activities.

4.3. Co-creation and stakeholder engagement – essentials

Co-creation activities span several design principles encompassing a multitude of definitions across disciplines, such as participatory design and open innovation. For instance, De Koning et al (2016) provide an analysis of 50 co-creation methods and definitions, presenting a comprehensive analysis of this concept. The result of this work clearly shows that while co-creation has been linked to several applications, a complete and coherent framework is still missing (de Koning, Crul, and Wever 2016). Moreover, while the multitude of theories offers a comprehensive analysis for better understanding of “co-creation” and of the importance of its application in cities, the methodology to perform such activities still remains difficult to be clearly identified among the different approaches. When drafting a co-creation strategy, the winning formula requires us to ask “with Who” (Sinek 2009). Narrowing down the wide typologies of stakeholders to be engaged in the co-creation journey not only adds an intrinsic value to the approach, but also helps to cultivate authentic and long-term relationships with final users by prioritizing them.

The co-creation approach is positioned at the start of the Service Design methodology, a broad discipline originally conceived in the service blueprint design as a tool for generating new ideas and service concepts (Shostack 1982). Service Design links relevant contributions to ignite new knowledge, such as the customer’s value proposition (Edvardsson et al. 2000), service interfaces that embody service offerings (Secomandi and Snelders 2011), service operations (Victorino et al. 2018) and supportive technologies that empower service innovation (Kieliszewski, Maglio, and Cefkin 2012). Service Design effectively puts into practice a range of methods to be deployed in the process of creating and acquiring new knowledge.

A complementary perspective to Service Design has been recently provided by the Living Lab community, where social and creative inputs are compiled together to generate innovations (Schuurman et al. 2015). In fact, Living labs are user-centred, open innovation ecosystems based on a systematic user co-creation approach, integrating research and innovation processes in real life communities and settings.

Within Living Labs, the operational approach includes the macro or organisational level connecting actors across the territory in co-creation; the meso-level involving activities specific to a sector part of the overall network, and finally the micro level focusing on the user’s engagement in the process (Schuurman et al. 2015). Essentially, Living Labs enact the co-creation of integrated solutions with users through disruptive technologies by following the whole innovation life cycle, both raising awareness on developing public services, while encouraging citizens to participate in the technical process and implementing policy-related agendas. In these initiatives, Living Labs operate as intermediaries between citizens, research organisations, companies, cities and regions for joint value co-creation, rapid prototyping or validation to scale up innovation and businesses. However, cities interested in co-creating with their citizens can face multiple challenges. Reaching out to and effectively engaging with users is neither simple nor straightforward, but can add a real great value to the exercise of co-creation and to the outcomes produced. Recently, with the issues faced by the global community due to the COVID-19 pandemics, it has been even more challenging to organise co-creation activities with new actors, in virtual communities, to effectively deliver the expected results (Spagnoli, van der Graaf, and Brynskov 2019). Each city has its own very specific needs and faces different challenges. For this reason, the co-creation approaches in a city must be specifically tailored to the

intrinsic city or region's socio-cultural, economic, and technological contexts. The specific result of the co-creation process should mainly focus on *how* things are designed within the process, and several methods and tools can be of great help from city to city in each specific context. A first step in this direction is to identify core principles of the design process within the city, customised to the specific local context.

The ULL multi-method approach has emerged to overcome these challenges by strictly focusing on co-creating and orchestrating local ecosystems, thus involving multi-stakeholder teams in the design process, with the final aim of fostering inclusion within urban and regional contexts. The analysis of the context in which an ULL is established is in fact very relevant to clearly identify where and to whom the co-creation approach is directed, and how the concrete expected outcome of co-creation is going to impact the local communities (Veeckman et al. 2013). These user engagement principles in ULLs are needed to provide a co-creation strategy that is effective for the final target audience. ULLs need to put in place specific stakeholder engagement strategies to be as much as inclusive as possible. In fact, within ULLs, users become equal contributors and co-creators.

ULL users are not a homogenous entity. They form a group constituted by different actors bringing many different resources and ideas to the innovation process, and who may also have different needs and requirements in the co-creation approach. Thus, the emphasis on collaboration between users with a common purpose and an effective stakeholder engagement throughout the whole co-creation process is essential for developing inspiring innovation within ULLs.

The importance of the engagement and alignment of the stakeholders' goal and vision to the specific co-creation strategy has been reflected in several literatures (Christensen and Walker 2003; Cooke-Davies 2000; Panda and Barik 2014). According to Donaldson and Preston, stakeholder engagement brings five relevant benefits to companies and institutions: (i) It solves problems; (ii) It helps management see the future; (iii) It is a facilitator of trust; (iv) Stakeholders are influential partners; (v) Stakeholder engagement can improve the company's public image (Donaldson and Preston 1995).

Several methodologies for stakeholder engagement start from the "strategy" to draft stakeholders' engagement and mapping (Taylor and Banchilon 2019), but this approach prevents us from focusing on the real actors of the co-creation process. Setting the objective first is of utmost importance before identifying the detailed categories of stakeholders to be involved in the process. As a starting point, the Five Step Approach proposed by Panda and Barik, starts from the 1) Engagement Strategy before moving to the 2) Stakeholder Mapping; then exploring the 3) Preparation Phase, conducting 4) Engagement, and finally drafting an 5) Action Plan (Panda and Barik 2014). This method allows for providing a necessary internal alignment and a common understanding of where we want our co-creation strategy to go in the end.

A currently made mistake is also to outline stakeholder engagement mainly as a communication exercise, while it should be related to the core business activities and it should be addressing not only the currently engaged users, but especially people who are usually taken out from this process (*ibidem*), to better focus the action plan for effective follow up. It is also crucial to involve internal stakeholders from a governmental or a business department. These key stakeholder groups should always be part of the process from step zero to learn from them in terms of previous successes or failures. Identifying potential champions or advocates is very important for the success of a stakeholder engagement strategy and operational plan within an ULL. Different analyses have pointed

out that citizens, when involved in the decision making process, develop a sense of ownership of the project itself (Shepherd and Bowler 1997; Shindler and Cheek 1999). The level of influence of each stakeholder group in the co-creation approach is crucial to assign value to the different categories of stakeholders and identify the ones to be engaged at the different stages of the journey. For this reason, inclusiveness policies are relevant to be implemented within Urban Living Labs aiming to co-create with all their potential interested stakeholders. Before analysing in detail the inclusiveness policies needed to be considered in a co-creation process within an ULL, we provide below the visualisation of a set of good practices guiding principles relevant for co-creating with the citizens in an ULL context.

Guiding principles for co-creating with citizens

Figure 12 Living Labs citizen-centred co-creation guiding principles

4.4. Co-creation Flow Chart for Urban Living Labs: tools and methods

Given that the set of tools to be used for co-creating are quite wide, for this specific work, we have selected only the most innovative and proven to be successful in an ULL context. The tools identified and presented in this Chapter build on the excellent work developed directly with cities and ULL in

some previous European Commission funded projects, such as UNaLAB (<https://unalab.enoll.org>), CITADEL (<https://www.citadel-h2020.eu>), SYNCHRONICITY (<https://synchronicity-iot.eu>), U4IoT (<https://u4iot.eu>), as well as on the different approaches analysed from the literature.

Out of this extensive set of tools, we have selected a few ones which will be further discussed in detail through a series of playcards (see Annex 1) providing information about the categories of stakeholders to be involved, goals, materials to be used for each methodology, the step by step approach to be implemented, as well as a series of tips to be considered while benefiting from these tools. The detailed playcards will also mention the literature review performed and some references to get more information about the tools.

A co-creation flow chart offers an entry point for practitioners to keep the bigger picture in mind. The reader is guided through the various phases and steps of the whole co-creation process, from *“Information, exploration and inspiration”* to *“Implementation, commercialisation and evaluation”* for effective stakeholder engagement. A rather simplified draft visualisation of how we envision the flow-chart is presented below, which considers mainly four different phases for enacting co-creation within cities:

1. Exploration & inspiration.
2. Ideation & design.
3. Planning & prototyping.
4. Experimenting & evaluating.

The definition of the four steps has been developed by analysing in the literature the different phases followed by both design research, service design, service ecosystem analysis and of the Living Labs methodology. These stages are an integral part of the integrative process presented in section 4.1. Integrative process can serve as guidelines that highlight all required steps while developing an ULL innovation project. Whereas here, concrete tools and methodologies that can be applied during co-creative activities are presented. Figure 13 presents different activities that can be undertaken during various ULL innovation project development stages. Additionally, it depicts successful tools that are applicable during “Problem space”, “Solution space” and “Deployment space” stages of the development of the ULL innovation project. What is also worth-noticing, the ULL Co-creation Flow Chart should be visualised as an agile, circular model open to continuous iteration to avoid making mistakes in the process (see Figure 13).

Figure 13 ULL co-creation flow chart

Phase 1: Exploration & Inspiration

Activity 1: Decide your challenges

Defining the objective and the main final goal of any co-creation strategy is crucial for identifying the right categories of stakeholders to be involved in the process throughout the entire approach. As seen in Paragraph X, before drafting any stakeholder engagement and mapping strategy, it is of utmost importance to be in contact with all the internal actors who might have an interest in the final result of the co-creation process. To this end, several tools can be of great help when identifying the main challenges of the co-creation approach for unleashing the power of generating innovative solutions within the city. Within this phase, the tools we suggest to use are: Brainwriting; the SWOT Diagram, Decision Matrix and the Strategy Map.

Activity 2: Define stakeholders and their needs

Identifying all the right categories of stakeholders to be involved in the co-creation process is also vital for the success of the innovation strategy. Any type of actor who might have an interest in the final goal of the co-creation approach should be considered to clearly define their needs, objectives and values. This process includes the stakeholder analysis and mapping, which as a final result allows for clearly envisioning the benefits produced by the co-creation strategy, as well as how to approach all the stakeholders at the different stages of the process. Visualising and understanding the different user personas helps not only the top level management, but especially the different actors who will have to implement the co-creation strategy with citizens to put themselves in the shoes of their final users for producing effective results and impacts in the targeted communities. The set of tools we

suggest the cities to implement within this activity are: *the Actors Map; Value Proposition Canvas; User Personas and Storytelling.*

Phase 2: Ideation & design

Activity 1: Set your co-creation journey

Understanding the local context and how to consolidate the stakeholder network is of utmost relevance before setting the co-creation journey, as explained above in Phase 1. The co-creation journey is a relevant process that allows city officials to frame the problem, envision alternatives and identify a set of ideas to be further conceptualised and designed. The co-creation journey aims to bring together all the potential stakeholders interested in the solution produced with the final goal to develop fresh and innovative concepts alongside the support from the citizens. Action planning is a crucial part of this process, as it enables us to discover more about our selected community, in terms of needs and expectations, to avoid a mismatch between their desire (ideas) and the end result. The co-creation journey should also provide a clear visualisation of the approach at all steps, either to the city officials who will implement the strategy, and for the final stakeholders who will use the end result of the co-creation process. The most effective set of tools to be used within this activity are: *PESTEL Analysis; Roadmapping; the Idea Dashboard and the Community Canvas.*

Activity 2: Conceptualise and design

Design conceptualisation is the process of generating ideas for finding an optimum solution to the design problem. After the stakeholders' mapping phase, the ideas co-created with the citizens need to be conceptualised in a clear and consistent way for finally being designed and implemented. The conceptualisation and design phase is the most crucial one in the co-creation process, as mistakes at this step might generate issues in terms of acceptance of the solution by the stakeholders. For this reason, it is important that citizens are especially involved in this process and contribute to the ingestion of ideas and analysis of their feasibility in real-life environments. Conceptualising a design requires gathering facts and information, processing them, determining the issue, brainstorming, preparing a visualisation of the ideas for producing and refining the final design for the citizens. This approach is relying on the specific characteristics of the local context that need to be considered thoroughly. The most effective tools we suggest to use in this process are: *Lego Serious Play; Co-Co Toolkit; the Walt Disney Method and the 6 Thinking Hats.*

Phase 3: Planning & prototyping

Activity 1: Define your operational plan

Set a clear co-creation strategy and a related operational plan ensuring all the needs of the targeted stakeholder are considered into the process and produce a relevant impact for them. Make sure to set specific deadlines in the short and long term, and especially, share the strategy with your stakeholders to engage them in the following prototyping and development phase, which is crucial for the success of the co-creation process. This activity includes a risk assessment analysis and the definition of a set of measures to prevent issues may be faced during the prototyping phase. Drafting

a storyboard can be really helpful to visualise all the steps needed to be undertaken in the operational plan of the co-creation strategy. The set of tools to use during this activity are: *Ambition Setting; Vision Development; 5 Bold Steps Strategy and the Basis SWOT Workshops.*

Activity 2: Prototype and develop

Before developing the final solution, especially if technologies and structural physical changes are expected to be developed within the cities, it is essential to test the proposed products and/or services with the targeted stakeholders. Citizens should be engaged both in the testing and the development phase of a solution produced within an Urban Living Lab, to make sure the final product or service is needed, useful and has all the features requested by the targeted audience. Multiple prototypes might be needed before developing the final solution and planning accurately all the steps for testing and validating the prototypes is crucial for generating a real impact in the final communities of an Urban Living Lab, which will be evaluated in the next Phase. The most effective tools we suggest to use during this phase are: *Design Sprints; Storyboard; Assumption Mapper and the Open Innovation Hackathon.*

Phase 4: Experimenting & evaluating

Activity 1: Test the solution

User testing is usually applied in user-centered interaction design to validate a product together with the final stakeholders. The testing phase aims at evaluating the ability of the solution developed to meet the users' needs and their expectations. The testing phase is not just a process for gathering opinions or comments from a set of potential users, but involves a clear set of systematic observations developed with the users in several iterations throughout the testing process. There are several possible tools to be used within this approach. The four tools we are suggesting to implement during this phase are: *Usability Testing; Prototype Testing Map; Blink testing and A/B Testing.*

Activity 2: Assess your impact

The final activity of the co-creation process aims to assess the impact produced by the entire co-creation process within the target audience identified in Step 1, Activity 2. The impact analysis can involve both societal, economic, environmental and technological indicators using both online and offline tools for evaluation. The impact assessment can take into account both short to medium and long terms' outcomes and impacts generated at the benefit of the targeted stakeholders and should involve in the process the same categories of users who were part of the co-creation strategy since the beginning. The set of tools suggested during this activity are: *I Like, I Wish, What If; Dotmocracy and the Monitor and Evaluate.*

4.5. ULLs and inclusiveness

ULLs represent new ways of interacting in the urban context, which creates novel opportunities for wellbeing and health, environment and equitable transitions towards resilient urban futures,

especially because the “*social and political inertia*”, which lead to “*hardened social structures and ways of thinking*” (Zantvoort 2017) about responding to societal challenges, can be disrupted in co-creation. In this sense, co-creation is often used interchangeably with co-production as a “*magic concept*” (Voorberg, Bekkers, and Tummers 2015) that at a strategical level entails the solution to core challenges in current societies.

However, the new forms of interacting and co-creation also bring new forms of knowledge, priorities, interests and activities to the agenda, and potentially new winners and losers. Urban citizens represent a range of interests, activities and desires for life in the city, and they also bring different skills and resources into the co-creation processes (Buijs et al. 2016; Kabisch et al. 2016; Leino and Puumala 2021).

Inclusion is thus closely linked to the outcome, as well as to the process of designing, facilitating and managing the wide set of activities, which are at the core of co-creation in ULLs, as discussed in earlier chapters.

Two main perspectives

When considering inclusiveness in ULL co-creation, two distinct aspects are relevant, namely inclusiveness in the process of co-creation in the context of ULLs, and inclusiveness of citizens in urban spaces as an outcome of co-creation.

First, inclusiveness in the processes of co-creation concerns the participatory engagements of citizens, where novel forms of co-creation have the potential to expand the groups and scope of participation in urban policy making and implementation and the groups of citizens that participate (Lund 2018). The partnerships being formed are here vital.

Participation in co-creative processes involves that citizens are active in the events and processes taking place; at a wider scale, they are urged to take on a role of being active citizens (Buijs et al. 2016; Voorberg et al. 2015). Moreover, the active citizen participation commands that public administrations and policy-makers are open to active citizen participation (Lund 2018) (and in contrast to openness concerning information when decisions are made). This involves participation by citizens; in co-creative processes – inclusive policy making and planning, and refers to the design and organization of co-creative processes in ULLs (Lund 2018).

Furthermore, co-creation in ULLs links to democratic governance (Brandsen, Steen, and Verschuere 2018; Voorberg et al. 2015). Co-creative processes entail a dimension of transforming urban governance practices towards more open arenas for joint exploration and design of urban services and transformations, as well as increasing access to data and decision making at various stages.

Hence, inclusiveness refers to not only participation of citizens in public policy making but also integration of a multiplicity of diverse, active citizens in co-creation processes within the quadruple helix, stressing social justice or equity as a core aspect of inclusive co-creation in urban spaces (Leino and Puumala 2021).

Secondly, the outcome of co-creation may be more or less inclusive. As a result of co-creative engagement within the quadruple helix, the city activities, places and communities may become more inclusive (Menny, Palgan, and McCarmick 2018), as for example inclusiveness in planning practices of

urban greenspaces demonstrates (Chen et al. 2019; Miller 2016), or in stimulating sustainable consumption lifestyles (Nordregio, Planning, and OTB Research for the Built Environment 2016). However, for increased inclusiveness also to be the outcome of co-creative engagement, existing and potential socio-spatial inequalities in the individual ULL must first be recognized.

Moreover, through engaging in inclusive co-creative processes, citizens may gain empowerment and build individual capacity which thus is also a potential outcome benefiting inclusive urban co-creation (Lund 2018). More comprehensive knowledge and data is often accessible to citizens and stakeholders, which provides bricks in building capacity to engage in complex and often highly knowledge-intensive urban issues.

Main topics and debates

Inclusion in co-creative engagements within the ULLs raises debates on both process and outcome that are useful to consider. Despite the “several difficult issues that are intertwined around the issue of co-creation, it still involves a whole new thinking about public service delivery and policy development” (Torfing, Sørensen, and Røiseland 2019). Co-creation has the potential to alter basic perceptions among and of public services into an arena of collaboration, policy and social innovation and enablement (Torfing et al. 2019).

In an urban context, the active backing of urban public policy-makers in local governments and among elected politicians are necessary, as one of the four pillars of the quadruple helix. Often, urban policy institutions and policy-makers are challenged by the complex and fluctuating urban policy problems, which not only concerns finding and implementing viable solutions. This equally concerns adapting governance to increasingly integrate citizens – as partners in policy making and policy experimentation through social innovation. While governmental actors are relatively keen to involve citizens and other civil society actors in the design and implementation of innovative solutions, co-initiation of public innovation is (still) rare. As a result, local governments often fail to tap into the experiences, ideas, and resources of civic actors when identifying and defining problems and challenges that call for innovative solutions (Sørensen and Torfing 2018).

Co-creation/co-production is here often considered to be a cornerstone for social innovation in the public sector (Voorberg et al. 2015). Inclusiveness is, and through enhancing democratic governance, and ensure shared ownership and joint knowledge, co-creation in the ULLs may also bring the hard-to-reach and multiple social groups into introducing (Voorberg et al. 2015) thus linked to two of the aims of social innovation (while the third aim of making public interventions more economically efficient is less salient). Thus, it is salient, and also an open question, exactly which forms of governance that arise out of co-creative processes – whether this be e.g. meta-governance, adaptive governance, mosaic governance, interactive governance, or local level empowerment (Buijs et al. 2016; Leino and Puumala 2021; Nevens et al. 2013; Torfing et al. 2012).

Furthermore, in the perspective of inclusiveness, Kabisch et al. point to the challenges for including active citizenship of multiple groups of citizens, and questions the capacity of traditional government for including the cultural diversity they represent in urban spaces (Kabisch et al. 2016). Active co-creation involving the urban diversity may support a move from “pre-defined issues and solutions towards reframing problems that open up the view on what interventions are needed and possible” (Leino and Puumala 2021).

For inclusion of citizens in co-creation in the ULLs, the social capital they bring into the processes of specifically designed co-creative processes is critical. Citizens without the necessary cultural and/or social capital are still likely to be excluded (Brandsen et al. 2018). Considering the social capital, it becomes evident how the access and competence of vulnerable groups among urban citizens is a crucial factor for inclusiveness of co-creative processes. In other words, even when the stated intention behind citizen participation in the ULLs is to increase inclusiveness in urban spaces, city decision making, and the provision of public services, the design of the co-creative processes may be less attentive to the needs and everyday practices of citizens with less social capital than those mimicking public officials or private facilitators in educational level, household status, income, ethnicity, etc.

Inclusion of active and diverse citizens and stakeholders entails questions such as who is included as stakeholders, at what stage of developing interventions or policies, how is co-creative engagements designed and facilitated. Alternative methods, including interactive, creative, digital methods have been suggested to invite citizens beyond the “usual suspects” of well-educated, middle aged citizens in for example strategic framing of inclusive futures (Pérez-Soba et al. 2018).

Furthermore, co-creation in-itself may be approached as inclusive (Nordregio et al. 2016), which concerns the values and perceptions embedded in co-creation. Here, co-creation is also a way to support identity-building, as well as to share and collect expert as well as local knowledge in the lack of data and adapt to informal activities.

5. Urban Living Labs data protection

ULLs have proven to be a fruitful way of connecting stakeholders, like regional policymakers, industry or civil society, in an urban environment. They not only provide test beds for validating solutions but define an environment for inter and transdisciplinary cooperation. This is highly connected to the generation and availability of urban data that is clearly one of the main requirements for urban research and innovation. Urban data labs can ensure that the research and innovation community jointly create and validate new approaches and solutions to eventually draw conclusions regarding the determinants of urban health and wellbeing. It should be no surprise then that contemporary legal and policy debates on privacy in smart cities and similar initiatives, such as living labs, are dominated by a debate focused on data and, therefore, on data protection laws (della Corte, van Loenen, and Cuijpers 2017).

According to Purtova (2018), we consider that most, if not all, of the data processed in a smart environment, such as the URBANOME ULLs, relates to a person at least in purpose or impact (Purtova 2018). This is so because one of the key goals of the ULLs, which is a common goal of many smart city and living lab projects, is to process data with the purpose of adapting the environment and influencing persons’ behaviour there. As such, ULLs data can be seen as constituting information that is used or is likely to be used with the purpose to evaluate and influence the behaviour of persons in the urban environment. In addition, ULLs are commonly formed in complex public-private-people partnerships (PPPP) including numerous actors, where personal data may be processed both for commercial and law enforcement purposes.

The unprecedented advances in the fields of citizen science and living labs have induced several issues regarding the data storage and protection of the participants’ personal data gathered within the living

labs activities. Related researchers and stakeholders are not always up to date with the best practices, posing thus a serious risk of data being compromised in pernicious actors. The threat of data during their acquisition, storage or transmission is of major importance. According to the General Data Protection Regulation 2016/679 (GDPR), improved data protection practices are necessary given the 1) convergence of increasing threats, 2) increasing difficulties in recruiting large population cohorts and 3) increasing ethical and legal burdens posed on the living labs researchers to protect personal data. Therefore, the remainder of this section aims to highlight the most important issues associated with the protection of the personal data gathered within the living lab activities and to provide a series of best practices serving as generic recommendations.

The GDPR defines personal data as any information that relates to someone who is identified or identifiable on the basis of that data (Art. 4(1) GDPR). An identifiable natural person is *“one who can be identified, directly or indirectly, in particular by reference to an identifier such as a name, an identification number, location data, an online identifier or to one or more factors specific to the physical, physiological, genetic, mental, economic, cultural or social identity of that natural person”*.

Data protection in the case of URBANOME

Specifically, in URBANOME the applications in the participating ULLs can be summarised as the collection of risk questionnaire data, data on movement tracking of individuals, biological sample collection (blood plasma, urine and saliva), medical examinations (e.g. spirometry, sleep recordings, neuropsychological examination) and secondary data analyses. In all the cases international/national guidelines/legislation in relation to collection and handling will be strictly followed for staff involved in this project, while ethics approvals will be obtained from the respective regulatory bodies.

It is therefore important to point out that the URBANOME ULLs data collection will take place for the specific and concrete objectives of the project and not for pursuing general and vague purposes. It will also promote the necessary and effective data collection to achieve the aforementioned purposes and not unsure experimentation which does not fulfil the project objectives. The data gathered within the ULLs will not be re-used for other, unrelated purposes such as to be shared with private companies that wish to test commercial products irrelevant with the ULL aims.

Another important point is the distinction between personal and non-personal data, collected and processed within the ULL activities. Indeed, ULL data collection involves also collection of environmental variables (pollution, temperature, noise levels, traffic level) not associated with a single participant but with city areas or participant clusters. These type clearly cannot be considered as “personal data”, thus do not pose any serious concerns from a privacy and data protection perspective and as such they will be open available to other researchers and/or stakeholders.

As far as it concerns the “personal” data collection, it is therefore clear that the URBANOME ULLs need to consider ethical and legal issues, such as data protection and privacy as key element to ensure that the project will strictly follow the relevant legislative framework and good practices. If you cannot guarantee data protection of your stakeholders/citizens, you will lose the trust of the panel. To this end, the activities within the URBANOME ULLs will be supervised by a Data Protection Officer (DPO) who oversees the data protection strategy and ensures compliance with the General Data Protection Regulation 2016/679 (GDPR).

Privacy refers to the participants' ability to control how their information is collected and how it is used. On the other hand, confidentiality refers to the risk that participants' identity might be revealed without their given permission upon enrolment (Jamieson and Salinas 2018). Although the literature regarding the case of living labs is relatively scarce, we have identified that the most common privacy or confidentiality threats are the following:

1. Data collection without the participants' explicit and informed consent.
2. Data management vulnerabilities inducing either malicious or accidental breaches resulting in data accessibility to non-authorized people which have not been identified during the data acquisition phase.
3. In case of data management solutions involving either Internet access or employing Application Programming Interface (API), there is serious susceptibility of unauthorised access from pernicious actors (Liu et al. 2012).
4. The former threat is further enhanced in the case of cloud environments where private information may be revealed due to a) human errors, b) connectivity glitches or c) external hacks.
5. Malicious access to the participants' personal data may revert the de-identification (anonymisation) procedure, especially in the case that the coding scheme is also accessible.

The overarching principle of URBANOME is that all studies in the project must strictly follow the regulations in national and international legal and ethical rules. Within URBANOME ULLs projects we will fully comply with ethical and legal principles in order to protect the dignity, rights, and welfare of research participants. This includes:

- The European Convention for the Protection of Human Rights and Fundamental Freedoms 1950.
- The Declaration of Helsinki 1964 (version 2018).
- The [Standards and operational guidance for ethics review of health-related research with human participants](#) (2011).
- The International Ethical Guidelines for Biomedical Research Involving Human Subjects (version 2016).

In addition, all activities must conform to the most recent European Union Directives. The charter of Fundamental rights of the General Data Protection Regulation (EU) 2016/679 ("GDPR") EU regulation on the protection of individuals with regards to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data must, without exceptions, be followed. European, national and institutional requirements and codes of practices need to be considered in all work tasks. Under the GDPR, any organisation that works with user data will be indeed required to clearly and understandably explain what they are collecting and why they are collecting it. Moreover, to collect personal data explicit consent is necessary and users are permitted to withdraw that consent without motivating it and thus have their data erased.

When and if appropriate as determined by the local Research Ethics Authority, for data collection from direct contact with human participants (e.g., during interviews, observations, or other means of monitoring), requirements include:

- **Written informed consent** for each participant and clearly explained information that she/he can withdraw from the study at any time without having to motivate her/his decision nor suffering any prejudice; and
- **Formal approval** from local Partner Institutional Ethics Authority to ensure that the highest ethical standards are being upheld.

More specifically, in the individual studies carried out in the URBANOME ULLs, study subjects who will be asked to participate in the ULLs activities are entitled to choose whether or not to take part. Their decision will be voluntary and they need to be informed to understand what is involved. Information needs to be given in both oral and written form, in the native language, by an authorised professional. The subject needs to be informed about the study purpose (including why the subject was selected to participate) goals, methods and expected benefits and risks. They need also to be provided with a description of any procedure and an estimated duration of required time for participating in the study. They need also to be informed about inclusion and exclusion criteria as well as whom they should contact for answers to any questions they may have in relation to the study.

The informed consent form needs to be developed in accordance with common practice and standard examples, as well as local ethics regulations, with relevant adjustments to reflect the study specifications. Details on how the study participants can request removal of their coded data from the study has to be provided in the informed consent form. Moreover, the informed consent provided to each subject needs to clearly explain she/he can withdraw from the study at any time without having to motivate her/his decision nor suffering by any prejudice. The consent form will need to be stored locally in the study subject's personal file, and it needs to be written in the national languages of the respective partners. The informed consent will need to ensure that participants have understood all information, and make a voluntary decision about whether to participate.

Published reports, scientific papers, etc. must not identify individuals, and any results have only to be presented at aggregated level. In compliance with the data protection acts which states that data are to 'be held no longer than is necessary' and to meet the requirements of data providers, at the end of URBANOME, data that could be potentially used to identify participants need to be destroyed.

The ULL projects are committed to ensure that the general benefits of their activities will warrant the involvement and efforts of their participant individuals, limiting any disturbance to them, especially in terms of protecting the identity and integrity of them. The projects need to enable mechanisms to avoid any intentional or unintentional use of data that can bring harm to any participant, or being misused in other contexts. All partners performing research will be required to follow agreed common rules for the recruitment of participants, the implementation of activities, recording, analysis and storage of data collected in the project.

All data collected will be stored anonymously on a secure server (i.e., URBANOME repository) that has restricted, password protected access and data encryption. An identification number will be assigned to each participant.

The transfer of data on human subjects to the URBANOME repository is only considered when: informed consents, ethics approval and – when applicable - approval by local data protection authorities cover the purpose that the data are envisaged to be used within URBANOME and allow transfer of individual or aggregated data to the URBANOME repositories.

All data that have been transferred and stored into the URBANOME repositories are completely anonymised. The Data Owner/Data Provider is responsible for the anonymisation process and for ensuring that identifiable variables are not transferred to the URBANOME repository. Directly identifiable variables include - but are not limited to - national ID number, name, phone number, ZIP-code, e-mail address, address, geographical coordinates (at a resolution that risks identification). One shall also be aware that a combination of just a few indirect identifying variables (such as birth data, gender, and zip-code) can be used to identify a large portion of individuals on any dataset. In this context, the Data Owner/Data Provider shall only provide such variables at the lowest possible resolution that is necessary for analysis, e.g., district instead of zip-code; year of birth or age instead of birth date.

It is useful to recall that the GDPR is an expansive set of regulations which cover the entire lifecycle of personal data. More specifically, there are four (4) articles that codify the URBANOME ULLs participant rights in terms of their personal data and how these are related with the data storage. These articles have been already taken into consideration by the URBANOME ULLs community and were also highlighted within the URBANOME Data Management Plan:

1. **Access rights by URBANOME participants** (GDPR Article 15): URBANOME ULLs participants are allowed to obtain detailed information about their data usage in terms of a) processing purposes, b) any disclosed data recipients, c) storage period duration and d) how their data will be used within automated decision-making approaches. So, the URBANOME storage system needs to be designed to store these metadata and to provide a timely access to them.
2. **Right to be forgotten** (GDPR Article 17): URBANOME ULLs participants need to be constantly granted with the right to require the deletion of their personal data without any undue delay. Therefore, the URBANOME storage system needs to be designed so as to be able to delete the requested data in a timely manner (e.g. 72 hours). This obligation needs to be also valid for any backup files or replicas.
3. **Data portability right** (GDPR Article 20): URBANOME ULLs participants have the right to ask to obtain in a commonly used format all their personal information being stored by the system. They can also have the right to request the direct transmission/dissemination of their data to another health expert or a third party. So, the URBANOME storage system should be capable of accessing and transmitting all their personal data in a timely manner.
4. **Objection rights by URBANOME participants** (GDPR Article 21): URBANOME ULLs participants have the right to decline at any time the use of their personal data for any research, publication, historical archiving or profiling purposes.

More in general, the storage and transferring of data need to adhere to national, institutional and EU policies, such as the FAIR Data Management guidelines, concerning safe storage and transfer of data. The URBANOME Ethic Advisory Board will do a thorough analysis of the ethics issues at every single ethic periodic report and will plan the measures that will be taken to ensure compliance with the ethics standards of H2020.

Incidental findings (IFs) are acknowledged to be among the most important ethical issues to consider in cohort-based studies that might reveal information about individual participants that are not related

to the research purpose, but may be relevant to those participants' future health. Incidental findings can be detected in any biological human specimen that is used for experimentation. Tissues, primary cells, blood, urine and saliva samples area among the specimens that incidental findings might be detected, after analysis of transcriptional products (DNA, RNA, proteins).

Up till now, there is no sufficient guidance of a standard policy that must be followed and usually every project or institute that conducts genetic research and genome-wide association study (GWAS) studies usually follows an empirical policy.

Within the URBANOME ULLs projects, multiple analyses of the human genome and metabolic pathways will be performed. The results of the data processing may provide previously unknown information to each volunteer about the existence of early clinical conditions of various pathologies or may indicate an increased likelihood of disease in the future due to the identification of a pathological expression leads to pathology or diseases.

In general, IFs should be returned if they reveal material risks that have:

1. Analytical validity.
2. Clinical significance.
3. Actionability.

and, if results can enhance treatment, if they concern a material risk, if they have clinical utility, if they are life-saving – then they should be disclosed.

Every laboratory in every different country of the project will report to the Medicine Doctor (MD) who cooperates with URBANOME and will be the responsible person to contact when solid results of a potential disease-related trait are identified and leads to a specific participant of the study or the cohort. When an IF arise and there are indications that it might be a possible threat for the health status of the participant now or in the future there are specific steps that must be followed before the researcher contact the principal investigator and the physician of the project:

In such cases, following the first indications of a possible serious condition, specific steps are taken:

1. Early findings or indications should be evaluated and confirmed by repeating the technique used in the first analysis.
2. Results should be confirmed, using techniques different from those performed by early analyses and by different researchers.
3. The specific pathological condition that potentially affects the outcome found as its severity (cancer, cardiovascular disease, respiratory, autoimmune diseases, etc.).
4. The study should be contacted by the bioethics committee and the study physician in order to inform the volunteer and plan treatment, treatment or contact specialist doctors. If the volunteer wishes, he or she reserves the right not to be informed of incidental medical data, information to be stated in the consent statement.

It is important to underline that the research carried out in the ULL projects will be conducted only by individuals with the appropriate scientific training and qualifications.

To sum up, the main aim of a robust data management plan is that the living lab researchers would shield the participants' privacy by ensuring that any data collection is used according to the specific project aims as explicitly stated within the informed consent form and the other recruiting materials. However, it should be clear that given the nature of modern cloud-based infrastructure and Internet networking, the complete elimination of all data protection vulnerabilities is an unrealistic aim.

The plethora of the available solutions enables the data scientists to select the most suitable one for each living lab. So, we refrain from specific suggestions since these are dependent from the type of data gathered, the participants' demographic characteristics and the project aims. However, our research activities within the URBANOME project have resulted in the formation of the following best practices that are generically applicable in every living lab scenario:

- The most fundamental best practice is that researchers ensure the proper and in-depth participants' information regarding the project aims and underlying activities during the recruitment phase.
- Data should be stored on password-protected computers using only secure services.
- Encrypt all communication messages and data collection procedures.
- Perform independent (preferably as a result of a randomisation algorithm) assignment of ID numbers to the participants.
- Data storage should be encrypted on-rest and end-to-end communications and password-protected.
- Codebooks or other participants' identification-related data should be stored locally and separately on encrypted storage devices. Ideally, these data types should be stored physically and not electronically at all.
- Prefer cloud storage only in the case of anonymised, raw big datasets.
- Use separate computers for living lab activities and other work or personal usage.
- Adopt the "privacy by design" concept through the description of the project vulnerabilities (e.g., the final prototype or the service produced by the living lab activities) on a design document so as end users and all relevant stakeholders to be aware of the potential security risks.
- Increase the secure storage of the personal data acquired through the living lab activities by applying server-level IP firewall rules during the access queries with the database located on the cloud infrastructure.
- Develop a proper brute force attack prevention technique in order to identify and avoid an infinite number of attempts to guess the password.
- Select and apply a suitable endpoint security system in order to protect the storage devices and the cloud infrastructure from cybersecurity threats. This best practice involves the selection of a robust antivirus software to provide comprehensive protection from sophisticated malware and evolving zero-day threats.
- Protect the cloud infrastructure associated with the living lab activities from a Distributed Denial of Service (DDoS) attack that aims to crash the associated online system by overwhelming it with data.
- Protect the associated data storage system by man-in-the-middle attacks which aims to interrupt an existing data transfer among two online storage devices by discouraging the attackers to pretend being legitimate users.

- Promote privacy and data integrity on the personal data stored on the cloud infrastructure by applying advanced cryptographic protocols (e.g., transport layer security/TLS).
- Promote data integrity among the various interconnected living lab storage devices or even across different living labs through the development of the most suitable instance replication procedures. This approach will allow the authorised users to connect to the source data store and read or consume the data by creating copies of them and not updating the original ones.
- Adopt a data exposure approach so as the API client application firstly filters the result it gets before returning the data to the user of the application. So, data scientists avoid the identification of sensitive information that may financially cost to the living labs and damage their reputations.
- Enhance the security of the cloud infrastructure by avoiding web parameter tampering attacks which may modify the user credentials, permissions or even the integrity of the stored data.
- Increase the security level by adopting software solutions for avoiding directory traversal attacks which may provide unauthorised access to directories or personal data files stored outside of the web root folder.

6. Best practices and lessons learnt

In this chapter, a set of best practices regarding various ULL activities has been provided. The presented best practises cover relevant aspects discussed in the earlier parts of this deliverable, and showcase inspirational cases from the URBANOME project, as well as other successful projects and initiatives.

A total number of 17 best practice cases, are depicted, all of them following the different steps of the process of developing a sustainable ULL. The case studies reveal the key elements that characterize the ULLs and aim to bring together stakeholders, to co-create, plan, prototype and develop solutions with an ultimate vision to scale them up.

As it was highlighted in the earlier parts of this deliverable, setting up and developing a sustainable ULL is a highly challenging task. There are many interconnected aspects that need to be taken into account. The provided best practices can serve as valuable real-life examples of maintaining different ULL activities for those who have just started their journey with ULLs. To better navigate the reader throughout the presented cases, a thematic categorization of the 17 best practices is provided.

The presented best practice cases are divided into three main categories:

Area 1: *Co-creation, ULL Real-Life Experimentation, Quadruple Helix - Multi-stakeholder Participation, Engagement.*

Area 2: *Multi-method approach, Capacity building, Responsible Research, Open Science, Open & Social Innovation.*

Area 3: *ULL setting up, ULL management & governance, policymaking.*

What is also worth mentioning, the selection and categorization of the 17 best practice cases, is the thematic reflection on research, open science, and social innovation as they fit well the URBANOME scope. Most of the best practice cases have been undertaken by the cities of Thessaloniki and Milan,

which belong to the URBANOME partnership and have a long experience in ULL activities. Below, the description of all 17 best practice cases can be found.

Area 1: Co-creation, ULL Real-Life Experimentation, Quadruple Helix – Multi-stakeholder Participation, Engagement

City	Riihimäki
Best Practice Case	Living Lab “Together more” Peltosaari (FI)
Aim/Scope	The Living Lab “Together more” in Peltosaari (Riihimäki city, Finland) focused on creating possibilities for easy participation in development of the local living environment, aiming at increasing a sense of community and enhancing the dialogue between municipality and citizens.
Approach	It involved three experimentation areas: 1) developing places for activities and meetings, 2) piloting activities and events, and 3) increasing communication between residents, organizations and municipality (Karlsson et al. 2016). The day-to-day activities of the ULL involved identifying opportunities for activities information sharing and bringing together relevant stakeholders. Residents, municipal officials, representatives of companies and organizations, as well as researchers were involved in all phases of the project from planning to evaluation.
Lesson(s) learnt	A positive lesson learnt was that the active communication and the enhanced cooperation of citizens and the municipality, thanks to the ULL’s interventions that helped to increase awareness of citizens’ activities and everyday needs, cultivate a friendly atmosphere in the neighbourhood among resident, while it also contributed to build trust among the involved parts, primarily due to the active physical presence in the area of the project manager, facilitating exchange of information and feedback (Karlsson et al. 2016). A less positive lesson was the difficulty to reach citizens and motivate them to participate in the actual co-development process (and especially in the initial co-creation stages), although many people did participate in events and activities when they occurred. Moreover, while existing community groups may provide a way into the community, they may have ingrained approaches and may not be open to input from new participants.
External resources	SubUrbanLab: https://jpi-urbaneurope.eu/project/suburbanlab/

City	Aarhus
Best Practice Case	A Living Lab approach to reducing household energy
Aim/Scope	The ENERGISE project deployed the living lab approach to reduce the energy use in households. A total number of 306 households from 8 European countries participated in the project, specifically targeting lower indoor temperatures and fewer laundry cycles.
Approach	The ULL was based on the social practice theory, which support the everyday behaviour transformation, through the engagement with norms, perceptions and conventions, compared with technologies, nudges or other policy instruments that seek to change behaviour more directly. The Living Lab methodology was applied in three stages (Sahakian et al. 2021): 1) a deliberation stage in which participants were recruited, relevant equipment (metering) installed, and baseline data on practices collected through surveys and interviews; 2) interventions: laundry and heating challenges were implemented for 3 months monitored through weekly surveys and interviews (challenge kits with tips and trigger equipment were provided); 3) follow-up surveys and closing events. Within the ULL context, the participating households interacted both with project holders (single interviews) and other households (focus groups).
Lesson(s) learnt	This case study shows that engaging with households through an experimental and learning-based approach may work when the approach disrupts and engages with routinized practices. Ongoing data collection served not only to inform researchers, but also to prompt participants

	to reflect on their practices. The ULL focused on stakeholders assessment, trying to understand what they gained through their participation in the process, what helped (or hindered) their behavioral transformation and how these finding could feed future activities of the ULL. Indeed, there were remarkable behavioral changes in terms of using energy in households, as well as changes in norms, habits, perceptions and knowledge, e.g. participants reflected critically on their previous, routinized practices.
External resources	ENERGISE: http://www.energise-project.eu

City	Milan
Best Practice Case	Milan Air and Climate Plan (PAC) co-construction (Piano Aria e Clima)
Aim/Scope	The Municipality of Milan gathers public views and recommendations on the occasion of “the Air and Climate Plan” (PAC) draft, by inviting and involving citizens in specially established thematic laboratories and Citizens' Table.
Approach	The public consultation is recognised and promoted as an experimentation and innovative method of involvement and interaction with stakeholders and citizens. The consultation on the “Air and Climate Plan” (PAC) provided the Municipality of Milan with valuable information and indications on the priorities for intervention, through the widest possible active citizenship and the strong interaction among citizens, experts and policymakers. Case studies and best practice policies from other cities were set on the discussion table, enriching interaction, experimentation and implementation. Straight communication and innovative tools/methods were used, either in virtual environments or in the frames of physical events/meetings to increase stakeholders engagement.
Lesson(s) learnt	PAC helped all the integral parts of the society -and especially policymakers and professionals – to acquire new competencies and skills, as well as a better understanding of the interaction dynamics among all the City of Milan different stakeholders and the need for equal representation even of the most marginalised and vulnerable citizens in policymaking. This approach also raised citizens’ awareness of the climate change impact, carbon footprint and air quality effects, as well as on the crucial role of their active participation towards their effective tackling.
External resources	https://partecipazione.comune.milano.it/processes/piano-aria-clima

City	Milan
Best Practice Case	Open Squares and Open Streets
Aim/Scope	The aim was to turn squares again into a vital part of the neighbourhood “life”; a core social & cultural meeting point, an integral part of citizens’ outdoor everyday living, that will no longer resemble a parking or a transit area.
Experimentation and implementation	The Municipality of Milan has actively collaborated with citizens not only to identify & implement, but also to maintain (squares) a common “vision” for City’s squares, transforming them into places that could host seasonal fests, tradeshow, open street events and other (non-commercial) initiatives, or just to become welcoming places for someone to go for a walk, exercise, meet friends or just to cross over before or after a demanding day at work.
Lesson(s) learnt	Use city as platform for creating new ideas, where the plurality of stakeholders, knowledge and ideas smash using inclusive, flexible, and participatory approach. The city is a boundless source of ideas but also a collaboration method between and with systems and communities. It proves “tactical urban planning” ¹ approach is an innovative way of doing urban planning, based on

¹ More information on tactical urban planning can be found here: <http://tacticalurbanismguide.com/>.

	short-term and low-cost interventions, to bring public space back to the center of the neighbourhood and the life of the inhabitants.
External resources	Piazze Aperte and Strade Aperte https://www.comune.milano.it/documents/20126/7117896/Open+streets.pdf/d9be0547-1eb0-5abf-410b-a8ca97945136?t=1589195741171

City	Milan
Best Practice Case	Community Garden
Aim/Scope	Citizens reuse abandoned -or not properly maintained by the municipality- public areas within the “urban fabric” setting, turning them into green spaces (ornamental greenery or vegetable gardens) to preserve city’s natural heritage.
Experimentation and implementation	Citizens become the main actors of this initiative, envisioning, designing & implementing independently the “Community Gardens”, joining their forces & vision under a common “goal” for the enhancement of their neighbourhoods. The project also attracted other community stakeholders to get involved, i.e., investors & designers, who got inspired by citizens’ work with the gardens, creating brain teasers for planners & further exploitation.
Lesson(s) learnt	Community gardening can play an important role in the social life of citizens in neighbourhoods, since individuals collaborate under a common “goal” for their small-scale society (Cognetti, 2014). On the one hand, Community Gardens can educate citizens to embrace & practice the urban sustainability fragile principles (Callon 2001), increasing both their environmental consciousness and their responsibility, since public gardens cannot exist without the community. Even the and production of goods here is an indirect outcome, outside the sphere of commodification. The public administration should focus its efforts to foster ‘co-creation’ efforts.
External resources	https://www.comune.milano.it/servizi/giardini-condivisi

City	Milan
Best Practice Case	Social Innovation Living Lab in Milan: Merezate+
Aim/Scope	Milan expands its urban borders, reshaping and regenerating the wider industrial metropolitan area to respond to the influx of new “white-collar citizens” and their lifestyle needs. The Milan Merezate+ project promotes an innovative, human-centred urban development model, through the mitigation of emissions in the area.
Experimentation and implementation	In the promoted urban development model citizens and the environment stand on the focal point of experimentation and decision making. The project constitutes a “brick” in a city, which needs to redesign its setting, offering to the new generation of its citizens a “place to live”. The Merezate+ project demonstrates how urban environments offer the potential for lifestyles with low environmental impact because high population densities are suited to sharing transport, energy and other resources. Cities across Europe, members of the Merezate+ network, including Municipality of Milan, have collaborated to reduce their environmental footprint and boost climate resilience running a number of social innovation experiments, engaging in some cases over 1000 citizens, to address urban and societal challenges, like the promotion low-carbon lifestyles.
Lesson(s) learnt	The emphasis has been set on building resilient communities, capable to foster grassroots initiatives and take the advantage of state-of-the-art ICT tools to monitor environmental impacts. One of the biggest obstacles towards this urban transformation has been the balance between citizens’ expectations or in other words the balance “what can implement” and “what we think that can be implemented”. In Milan’s case has been proved very hard to make large-scale commitments, regarding capital and regulatory change, as citizens envisioned.
External resources	https://www.climate-kic.org/success-stories/milan-merezate/ https://www.climate-kic.org/programmes/deep-demonstrations/healthy-clean-cities/publications/

City	Milan
Best Practice Case	Sharing Cities - Milan
Aim/Scope	Sharing Cities is a European project funded by the Horizon 2020 program - Smart Cities Lighthouse - which aims to create a "smart" neighbourhood with "almost" zero emissions, to respond to the main environmental challenges of cities and improve the daily life of its inhabitants.
Experimentation and implementation	To achieve its objective the City of Milan promoted the urban service sharing. Although it flourishes locally, it is still a relatively limited practice, since citizens very often feel scepticism towards sharing and experience mismatch with expectations. In the case of Sharing Cities, small-scale interventions with targeted, but also representative groups of stakeholders, were implemented to increase the trust towards urban sharing.
Lesson(s) learnt	Using large working groups and digital/online settings for interaction and experimentation among wider audiences may not necessarily be enablers, but rather a barrier for sharing experiences, views, concerns or change beliefs. Milan's small-scale interventions, within the SmartCities context, had a positive impact, increasing trust for urban service sharing. It is very important to involve every time the largest number of people to work with, but it is more important to ensure that the reached information equally represents all the involved, targeted stakeholders (quality VS quantity). Equal representation and promotion of interaction dynamics among all the members of the society (public/private sector, experts, citizens) is one of the key aspects for effective participatory research and innovation, as well as for building trust. It has proved how interoperability (between different entities through common guidelines, technologies and standards) can foster real participation from private and public stakeholders. It also highlights the importance of governance processes and adoptability.
External resources	Sharing Cities – Milan: https://www.sharingcities.eu/sharingcities/city-profiles/milan

City	Milan
Best Practice Case	Regeneration of large-scale social housing estates through living labs
Aim/Scope	The SoHoLab project's main focus was to promote the regeneration of large-scale social housing estates, by promoting a series of recommendations and suggestions to improve the related regeneration actions, strategies, policies and plans.
Experimentation and implementation	To achieve this, SoHoLab adopted and promoted the Living Lab methodology, as a means to understand and evaluate how the primary targeted stakeholders -residents, housing associations and other intermediaries- can be effectively involved in the social housing estates' regeneration.
Lesson(s) learnt	The adopted methodological approach highlighted the need for increase the active participation of citizens in the public dialogue and promote various consultation modes (more inclusive & interactive), since city dwellers appeared unwilling to be represented by any single policymaking entities. An interesting outcome was that <i>"the problem is not that people do not speak, but the fact that they are not heard"</i> . Whistle-blowers should also be not be ignored. These active public figures are not only concerned about protecting their own interests, but also serving the common good. The Living Lab approach promotes active citizenship and the citizens can act as real "whistle-blowers" for the society. The importance of public spaces, likes shops is also quite important for promoting public debate and deliberation (Habermas 1988; Turner et al. 1994). Shops are places where very different, intersecting people come into contact, and where multiple forms of expression and a truly political discourse can arise.
External resources	SoHoLab: www.soholab.org SoHoLab on JPI Urban Europe website: https://jpi-urbaneurope.eu/project/soholab/

City	Milan
Best Practice Case	Awareness generation and promotion of NBS
Aim/Scope	The CLEVER Cities project aims to drive a new kind of nature-based urban transformation for sustainable and socially inclusive cities across Europe. In case of Milan City, Urban Living Lab namely CLEVER Action Labs (CAL) ULL1/CAL1 focusing building green roofs and walls under “Regreening Milan”
Experimentation and implementation	To achieve this, CLEVER Cities has adopted living lab methodology and co-design approach, as a means not only to increase knowledge about the importance of greenery in the buildings, but also to adopt a more strategic approach to public interest communication and what and how to evaluate the primary targeted stakeholders (residents) can be effectively involved in the “Regreening Milan”.
Lesson(s) learnt	The adopted methodological approach highlighted the importance of: role of citizen as a “co-producer” in co-design approach and “Sustainable Engagement” (continued communication among stakeholders). The need for ‘Adaptability and flexibility’ surfaced during the COVID-19 resulting in withdrawing interest of many applicants (people) to build NBS. The administrative and bureaucratic procedures resulted to be the hardest barriers in the co-design and co-implementation of NBS, particularly of residential condominiums, and authorization procedures.
External resources	CLEVER Cities Clever cities guidance Co-creation Pathway for Urban Nature-Based Solutions: Testing a Shared-Governance Approach in Three Cities and Nine Action Labs Co-Creation Pathway as a catalyst for implementing Nature-based Solution in Urban Regeneration Strategies Learning from CLEVER Cities framework and Milano as test-bed

City	Thessaloniki
Best Practice Case	Play4 / Participate4 Common Cause Campaigns
Aim/Scope	Gamification of the social participation & active citizenship to raise awareness and maximise the impact of a common cause for the society
Approach	The “Play4” campaigns, launched in 2017 by Thess-AHALL, constitute a successful case example of awareness raising campaigns, by deploying gamification means. In the “Play 4” campaigns, the public is invited to visit hospitals, nursing homes, patient associations to play and exercise through digital novel technology, e.g. the webFitForALL serious game platform, so as the collected points to be turned into special donations (gifts or other benefits) for the hosting organizations in-need. In some cases, the whole city or parts of it transformed into an alternative “amusement park”, where citizens, NGOs and policymakers participate to service a common goal or increase awareness of a societal problem (e.g. the “Play4” campaigns on the 2017 International Parkinson’s Awareness Day and the 2018 World Autism Day, when the central squares of Thessaloniki and Veria cities, turned into “serious gaming playgrounds” to fight the stigma experienced by the targeted populations). The “Participate4” is the sister-project of the “Play4” campaigns. The main difference is that the “Participate 4” campaigns gamify participation by deploying open science and open research means (public lectures, workshops, field visits in the university/outside in the city, training events). In this case, citizens’ participation is translated into credits which service a common cause.
Lesson(s) learnt	The gamified awareness campaigns enhanced interaction among the community and institutionalized or other marginalised population groups. Through their collaboration to serve a common cause, different actors of the society bridge the existing gaps among them, listen to

	<p>each other needs and problems and fight stereotypes, which in most of the cases exceed the initial aim to donate to an organization or a group of people (Mantziari et al. 2019). The entertaining way of playing games and educational or learning-by-doing activities proved a valuable tool for community researchers, while it also cultivated a new notion over terms like “social inclusion – social participation and innovation”. The Play4/Participate4 campaigns strengthened the institutions’ extroversion and introduced the future nursing homes as structures open to the local community. The Play4/Participate4 was one of the Parent-Ideas of other successful case-studies, including the SISCODE H2020 “Partners of Experience” programme (see next case).</p>
External resources	<p>Mantziari, D., Petsani, D., Konstantinidis, E., et al. Ageism and open Academia: exploring new pathways towards the limitation of social exclusion of older adults and chronic patients. In: Oral Presentation at the European triple helix congress on responsible innovation & entrepreneurship (ETHAC2019), Thessaloniki, Greece, 30 September–1 October 2019. LLM Care: https://www.llmcare.gr/participate4/ https://www.llmcare.gr/paizoume-gia-ton-aftismo-me-to-olokliromeno-systima-frontidas-ygeias-llm-care-sti-veroia/ SISCODE: https://siscodeproject.eu</p>

City	Thessaloniki
Best Practice Case	Let’s sail with “CAPTAIN”
Aim/Scope	Older Adults envision & co-create the “CAPTAIN” eCoach, a smart home assistant that provides personalized advice & support in their everyday living, whenever & wherever is needed.
Approach	<p>As a smart home assistant, the CAPTAIN eCoach system uses “transparent” state-of-the-art technology to provide a radically innovative & user-friendly UI to enhance the empowerment of people in need of guidance and care. It supports setting goals, getting feedback along the process until the goal achievement. Goals are referred to four domains that enhance wellbeing in everyday life: Cognitive-Physical-Social-Nutritional. The whole system was envisioned, co-designed, experimented, tested & validated, step-by-step with stakeholders (older adults & formal/informal caregivers), adopting the Agile Development Methodology, in the four LLs of the project, running in parallel across Europe for over 3 years (Greece – Cyprus – Spain – Italy – Ireland) (Tessarolo et al., 2021).</p>
Lesson(s) learnt	<p>The involved stakeholders, members of the CAPTAIN community, operated as both “ambassadors” & alternative researchers of the four LLs, having the sense of being part of a transnational group of people, who collaborate to achieve the same goal. It was the CAPTAIN Community that led the AUTH Medical Physics & Digital Innovation Lab and the Thess-AHALL to establish since 2018 the “Collaboration & Research Community for Independent Living” an alternative group of citizen researchers (people over 65 y.o. but also other stakeholders), who closely collaborate with the Lab & the Living Lab in participatory research activities, open science & training sessions, common cause events, entertaining events and field visits (i.e. outside in the city, museums, galleries). Moreover, the CAPTAIN methodology is a great example of applied participatory research with respect to the principles of co-creation & prior to all to stakeholders real needs & wishes. The CAPTAIN project partners did not hesitate to reject features of the system & pivot some parts of the developed technology to meet the needs of system’s end-users.</p>
External resources	<p>F. Tessarolo, D. Petsani, V. Conotter, G. Nollo, G. Conti, M. Nikolaidou, G. Onorati, P.D. Bamidis, and E.I. Konstantinidis (in press). Developing ambient assisted living technologies exploiting potential of user-centred co-creation and Agile methodology: the CAPTAIN project experience, J. Ambient Intell. Humaniz. Comput. (2021).</p> <p>CAPTAIN: https://www.captain-eu.org/ CAPTAIN Coach: https://www.captaincoach.gr/ Living Lab Projects of 2018: https://issuu.com/enoll/docs/401202620-living-lab-project-award-2018</p>

City	Thessaloniki
Best Practice Case	“Partners of Experience”
Aim/Scope	A life-long learning programme for “early-stage” researchers over 65 years old to enhance active citizenship and tackle the risk of ageism within the society.
Approach	Within the context of SISCODE project, the Thess-AHALL opened the AUTH University doors to older adult citizens, launching the “Partners of Experience” life-long learning programme to fight ageism. Older adults become members of an experiential research group to co-explore and co-create solutions for key societal problems of their everyday living in their city (e.g. urban environment, active citizenship, public health and social welfare). Following the research methodology (step-by-step, but in a more experiential way), the “Partners of Experience” set their research questions, participate in intergeneration activities with students and researchers (joint lectures, desk research, LL experimentation), while they also turn the core centre of Thessaloniki into a real-life experimentation playground (field visits, interaction with regional authorities). The programme has been supported by the AUTH Lab of Medical Physics and Digital Innovation, the Municipality of Thessaloniki and local NGOs (Konstantinidis et al. 2019; Mantziari et al. 2022).
Lesson(s) learnt	Follow-up surveys to older adults and self-evaluation sessions with the Thess-AHALL team were deployed throughout the co-design and prototyping phases of the “Partners of Experience” lifecycle. The overall assessment has shown older adults’ wide acceptance of the proposed methodology, as well as positive impact in their social life. The 45 experiential researchers became programme’s “ambassadors”, inviting new fellows to join. Municipality’s interest to implement citizen’s solutions and replicate the programme to other societal challenges, has been an additional highlight. The collaboration of citizens with local policymakers has led them to perceive themselves as part of Thessaloniki’s “active citizens” community, as well as to feel that their views/concerns are heard. Through their interaction with the AUTH university, citizens got familiar with the educational & research procedures, changing their belief that the Academia is a close “elite”, which does not care of society’s real needs. On their side, university students and researchers realised the value of the so-called by them working on solutions “FOR and WITH citizens; FOR and WITH the city”.
External resources	SISCODE: https://siscodeproject.eu/thess-ahall/

Area 2: Multi-method approach, Capacity building, Responsible Research & Open Science, Open & Social Innovation

City	Thessaloniki
Best Practice Case	Teaching co-creation and living lab methodologies to university students
Aim/Scope	Teaching the principles and value of living lab approach & co-creation to postgraduate medicine students through intergenerational, joined classes with chronic patients
Approach	Joint classes – lectures and hands-on sessions – of AUTH School of Medicine postgraduate students with older adult Parkinson’s patients-members of Thess-AHALL’s Collaboration and Research community for Independent Living – to perform co-creation activities, so as students to become familiar with patients’ community and their real needs, build trust with them and run effective problem-solving and solution-design, based on end-users requirements, thoughts and concerns.

Lesson(s) learnt	AUTH, through the Thess-AHALL, designed a first prototype course through experiential learning activities and active experimentation, by bringing students and citizens in the same class and triggering knowledge exchange through the mutual collaboration and support of all the involved parts. This round of joint lectures led students to promote the design of serious games for Parkinson's patients to support their everyday living and contribute to the alleviation of disease's symptoms, by respecting the feedback of older adults in a way that could meet and perform activities, based on end-users' needs, previous experiences and concerns about the disease (Bamidis et al. 2020; Konstantinidis, Petsani, and Bamidis 2021).
External resources	i-Prognosis H2020 (http://www.i-prognosis.eu/) and "Course on Technology", powered by the Board of European Students of Technology (BEST), Thess-AHALL & AUTH Lab of Medical Physics and Digital Innovation

City	Thessaloniki
Best Practice Case	Tips & Tricks For RRI
Aim/Scope	"Tips & Tricks for Responsible Research & Innovation" card deck to enhance co-creation, innovation and action among multiple stakeholders for effective solution design & policymaking. The cards include 20 "provocations" and "values" to inspire and challenge people to conduct effectively RRI and stakeholder engagement.
Approach	The "Tips & Tricks for RRI" cards have been inspired, created, and designed by Knowle West Media Centre (KWMC) and ENoLL, in collaboration with Thess-AHALL, as external third-party expert in LL & RRI methodologies. The wording and illustrations, as well as the final selection of the card were all co-creation outcomes from the SISCODE and NewHoRRizon projects, co-creation and co-validation workshops with Responsible Research & Innovation practitioners, and the KWMC Bristol Living Lab practice and research.
Lesson(s) learnt	The "Tips & Tricks for RRI" cards are used as discussion-starters and creative collaboration tool to help stakeholders and Living Labbers reflect on their work and explore new perspectives and possibilities. It is impressive the fact that academics, experts in-field, designers and community activists joined their forces to build a dynamic tool that could effectively respond to various settings of participatory research and societal/urban challenges. Despite the fact that the cards are products of stakeholders' co-creation, they reflect European Commission's principles for ethical, collaborative, inclusive, open and learning RRI, as well. Not only the cards as a final outcome, but also the interaction among all the contributors towards their designing, operated as drivers for knowledge exchange and cultivation of new perceptions of participatory research, co-design, stakeholders' dynamics and policymaking.
External resources	NewHoRRizon: https://newhorizon.eu/ SISCODE: https://siscodeproject.eu About the Tips & Tricks initiative: https://newhorizon.eu/tips-tricks-cards-for-rri/ Board with cards: https://padlet.com/enollorg/TipTrickRRI

City	Thessaloniki
Best Practice Case	City Science Initiative (CSI) – Urban Research Ecology Initiative
Aim/Scope	The City Science Initiative, powered by the EC JRC, provides an opportunity for cities, city networks, experts and the services of the European Commission to reinforce their cooperation and strengthen the science and policy interface with an aim to address more effectively and in a resilient way key societal and urban challenges.
Approach	The initiative has established five working groups on core urban and societal challenges for Europe, which are led by an equal number of European cities (or regions): Air Quality (Paris), Circular Economy (Hamburg), Mental Health & Wellbeing (Thessaloniki), Sustainable Mobility (Cluj-Napoca), Tech and the City (Reggio Emilia). The CSI promotes interaction, consultation and

	knowhow exchange among the leading cities and other European cities, which participate in the network, fostering new synergies and dynamics, in which citizens science and participatory research can help address the urban challenges in a resilient way and to develop a structured approach to evidence-informed policy-making at cities' level. Among other working topics, the city of Thessaloniki, represented in the CSI by the Municipality and the Aristotle University of Thessaloniki, has set on its focal point the human-centred research and co-creation approach, as well as multi-stakeholder engagement in cities, to address mental, social health and wellbeing challenges and crisis (e.g. the COVID-19 pandemic) within cities' everyday living urban setting.
Lesson(s) learnt	Joint sessions, concept papers, thematic events and a first attempt to pilot the CSI principles in the local contexts of cities highlighted the importance of the CSI network of the resilience of cities, the effective policymaking and challenge addressing at the regional, but also at a cross-national, EU level. Citizens and their needs stand on the centre of Initiative's interest and activities, while the consultation of policymakers, researchers and experts in social & open innovation act as a "complementary driver" for engagement, cultivation of new behaviours, values, beliefs towards a more sustainable, responsible and educated society.
External resources	https://ec.europa.eu/jrc/communities/en/community/3393/library/documents https://ec.europa.eu/jrc/communities/en/community/city-science-initiative

Area 3: ULL setting up, ULL management & governance, policymaking

City	Leoben
Best Practice Case	City Lab Leoben Austria
Aim/Scope	The aim of the City Lab Leoben Austria has been to develop citizen participation in policymaking to close the gap between citizens and policymakers, and create a strong community capable to meet new urban challenges.
Approach	The City Lab Leoben Austria was set up with the cooperation of researchers, civil servants and local stakeholders, as a physical and mobile space for collaboration, co-creation, design and discussions among various stakeholder groups (Scholl et al. 2017). Specifically, the City Lab was to facilitate the so-called "Future Experiments", i.e. participatory workshops to create new ideas for "a needs-oriented, sustainable and smart city". The City Lab was created following a process of a mapping of local governance structure and a co-design process, consisting of meetings, workshops and focus groups with the local community. A second, parallel, process in Leoben involved interventions to increase cooperation between citizen-driven initiatives and the city administration. One example was the initiative of local citizens to support and enhance communication with refugees in 2015, which led to a multi-stakeholder, participatory reflection and evaluation process, based on needs analysis, expert interviews, participatory observation, media analysis, focus groups/ workshops and surveys.
Lesson(s) learnt	The City Lab Leoben is itself an outcome of the Living Lab-based approach and co-creation among stakeholders. As an ULL, it is expected to foster further experimentation and participation to envision new urban development strategies that integrate the needs of citizens. The co-creation approach to "citizen-city" cooperation around refugees also fostered trust among the involved actors and contributed to implementation of a number of social inclusion projects involving refugees. Since one of the ULL's objectives is to cultivate legitimate solutions through the wide and representing inclusion of various stakeholders, a critical point of this case example was the limited engagement of the non-refugee support proponents.
External resources	https://jpi-urbaneurope.eu/project/urbexp/

City	Thessaloniki
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Best Practice Case	SI4CARE – Transnational Living Lab
Aim/Scope	Establishment of the SI4CARE transnational Living Lab in ADRION area as a driver for social innovation in Healthcare for the ageing population
Approach	The Thess-AHALL, as external expert of the Regional Development Fund of Central Macedonia participates in the SI4CARE Interreg project to transfer knowhow and the methodological tools for the establishment of a Transnational Living Lab, focusing on the social innovation and digital transformation of healthcare for older adults in ADRION area. In this city, co-creation and co-experimentation scale from the urban setting to the cross-border setting, transforming a whole region in the south-eastern Europe into a transnational social innovation ecosystem. The SI4CARE Transnational Living Lab operates as a cooperation network, actively involving regional stakeholders from the quadruple helix (policymakers, healthcare tech/service providers, citizens/older adults, researchers/academic partners and innovation experts), who strongly collaborate in two levels: first at a local/regional level, mapping the local challenges and needs and then, at the cross-border level, co-designing, experimenting, monitoring and evaluating various Social Innovation approaches, policies, care models, digital solutions and action plans for the older adults.
Lesson(s) learnt	Although it is still in progress (the project ends in 2023), the ten participating partners from seven countries, have started the exploration of the LL methodology, within their own ecosystem and context. So far, partners established their local stakeholder networks, which, in turn, became part of LLs transnational network, sharing common values and practices. The Living Lab members have their own board, apply participatory design approaches to address, experiment and validate solution for the local and the ADRION area challenges for older adults' health and care. An interesting lesson-learnt, so-far, has been the interaction among different stakeholders from different urban and cultural settings, in a way that cultivates the sense of belonging to the same community for servicing a common “goal”: the “who we are” at the local level turns into the “who we are” at the transnational level.
External resources	https://si4care.adrioninterreg.eu/

7. Conclusions and future challenges

ULLs are active sites of experimentation, contributing to generate new knowledge and validate solutions within diverse aspects of urban challenges. As such, they are predestined for testing, trialling, demonstrating and initiating the spread of knowledge, practices and socio-technical solutions beyond their immediate remit. They provide the perfect test bed for implementing the integrated approach, involving all the target groups of the quadruple helix to co-design, co-create, test and reach an agreement of what works well and can be adopted into urban strategies and what needs improvement. Up to now, experience has shown that ULLs contribute to exploration and inspiration, ideation and design, planning and prototyping, experimentation and evaluation, and several good practices clearly showcase that.

More than that, ULLs have the power to impact policies, at the urban level and even raise recommendations for actions needed to be taken at regional, national or European level in order to improve sustainability, liveability. In addition, ULLs have the power to scale up the approach, design, provide outcomes of the local experimentation and even transfer it in order to create growth and support several societal challenges, such as health and wellbeing.

The integrative methodology to set up an ULL and run the co-creation process, as well as tools that can be used and data protection issues have been addressed in this deliverable. Additionally, 17 best practices cases have been selected and depicted as paradigms that best reflect, in a holistic way, the

integrative process and the key elements of the ULLs. The best practice cases have been categorised in order to enable the reader navigate throughout them, considering the aims pursued and the elements on which more information and knowledge is sought.

As depicted throughout the best practice cases, ULL setting and running experience shows that several important conditions need to be satisfied in order to maximise the impact of the ULLs. These are listed and briefly discussed below.

A clear aim and realistic expectations

ULLs do not necessarily aim at transformative change as such, and often do not provide the resources for diffusion beyond their boundaries. New actors may be needed in order to coordinate and (further) support the co-creation and integration of local experiments within broader transition schemes at the urban level. Despite their proliferation in the European policy sphere, and their undoubted success as a vehicle to generate public funding, we need a careful reflection of the urban actors' expectations towards ULLs, by taking into consideration the power of people that are on board and committed towards delivering change. ULLs are not the "*new panacea*" in the urban governance arena.

The importance of involving one leader

Despite the promise of ULLs to leverage public and private bodies participation and inclusive decision-making through cross-sectoral collaboration, there is at the same time a need to remain cautious about the risks implied in such experimental governance arrangements for "organized irresponsibility" (Beck 1998), instances where society becomes a laboratory, but there is no one responsible nor held accountable for its outcomes.

Inclusive governance: leave no citizen behind

Kronsell and Mukhtar-Landgren (2018) call attention to the need to elaborate on democratic aspects for inclusion, legitimacy, power and transparency and how these institutional values relate to the different roles that people undertake within the ULLs (Kronsell and Mukhtar-Landgren 2018).

Justice and acknowledgement of citizens

By acknowledging that citizens can be capable actors to influence transformations, rather than just enablers of quick solutions, this can boost the process and shed light on the limitations of the technocratic approach to policy-making. Interventions can be more effective when co-designed by public officials, experts, behavioural scientists and citizens having an equally important role and involvement in the co-production process.

Embodiment of ULL outputs in strategies and urban policies

Taking ULLs beyond experimentation requires great care and attention for its interrelations with the more "*orthodox*" and official structures and institutions in urban policy and governance, such as strategic planning and urban design. Breaking silos among organisations in order to really achieve integration in policies is a challenging but a much needed step.

Reflection on replicability

Dealing with the inherent controversy between context or place-specificity and replicable elements of urban experiments requires reflexivity to abstract, parametrise and or contextualise these elements and design adaptive implementation processes in new places, organizations, sectors and policies.

Wise use of ICT to achieve a truly citizen-centric space

ICT shows advantages, and according to many concepts, currently plays a key role in fostering public engagement to achieve smart sustainable city objectives. Especially the IoT has recently started being combined with behavioural insights to nudge citizens toward decisions conducive to policy goals. According to recent studies focusing on the urban context, it is not clear yet whether data-driven nudges are conducive to promoting a truly citizen-centric space (Ranchordás 2020). As an example, citizens might be merely interpreted as passive subjects that need interventions aimed at harnessing their cognitive and motivational deficiencies (HERTWIG 2017).

Sustainability beyond the lifetime of the project

One of the reasons why individuals involved in ULLs lose interest and thus ULLs lose their dynamic and the momentum is the strong link with an EU project that in the best case, has a lifetime of four years. Creating impact on (health and wellbeing) policies is not a decision that needs to start and end within the project itself, but needs to have a solid basis and constantly seek for resources and funds. ULLs are often so focused on the societal challenge they address, that they forget about funding beyond the end of the project. Resource management must be a separate action plan that needs to be drafted at the beginning of the ULLs' life and be dynamically reviewed.

Future challenge

The emerging techno-urban field of the smart and sustainable city is deemed to be a powerful tool to support ULLs. However, there is still the need for frameworks that drive the practice of integrating technological and people-oriented approaches to a smart-city development. ULLs have been brought forward as experimental governance schemes that foster collaboration among different urban stakeholders in co-designing, co-developing, and testing *ad hoc* innovative solutions for site-specific urban sustainability problems. At the same time, they still face various challenges, such as the long-term involvement of a diversity of actors, fair procedures that allow the inclusion of diverse bodies of knowledge, their financial stability beyond projects that led to their development, seclusion of knowledge in the ULLs and a lot more.

It is of critical importance to investigate how the exemplary behaviourally-informed interventions that have been presented in this Handbook can contribute to effectively achieve the goals of ULLs, as spaces for cooperation and engagement in the urban transition to improve health and wellbeing. More than that, the ULLs need to identify spreadable models out of sustainability experiments, while keeping them modular and flexible in order to (re-)contextualise and adapt to specific needs. Once they achieve so, it is important to scale up from an individual local niche experiment to achieve broader system change. Figure 14 illustrates the steps that can be undertaken by a ULL to make an impactful change.

Figure 14 The process of making impactful changes within ULLs

Local experimentation reflects the embodiment of an experiment, the adoption and integration of its design, approach and or outputs into existing local structures, for instance institutions, regulations, planning, or even other communities of practice. Scaling-up reflects the horizontal diffusion of the experiment's results; the parametrization - reproduction and replication of its elements, design, or approach elsewhere. Translation deals explicitly with changing the context of an experiment, for instance spatially, institutionally, sectorally. Transferring refers to the internal development and growth of niche experiments, capturing the ways in which an experiment becomes bigger in terms of content and remit.

Efforts need to be taken to maximise the impacts of placed-based experimentation with the use of ULLs, in order to maximise their impact not only for the community that hosts them, but also for long-term sustainability transitions at a greater level.

All the factors depicted above are suggested to be taken into consideration towards inclusive, just, sustainable and impactful ULLs in general and specifically in URBANOME project.

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Annexes

ANNEX 1: Tools for co-creating with cities

<h2>Brainwriting</h2>	
<p>Phase 1</p> <p><i>Exploration & Inspiration</i></p> <p>Activity 1</p> <p><i>Decide your challenges</i></p> <p>Materials</p> <p><i>Paper sheets and pencils</i></p>	<p>Description</p> <p>Brainwriting is a tool for quickly generating ideas and solutions to a problem. Ask participants to write down their ideas about a particular problem on sheets of papers for a few minutes; then, each participant passes their ideas on to others for adding new ideas. The process repeats until sheets are collected for immediate discussion.</p> <p>Goals</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Produce a lot of ideas in a very short time frame ▪ Inspire true creativity by implementing an anonymous approach ▪ Allow people to evaluate others' ideas in a concentrated and creative way
<p>Step-by-step</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ <i>Step 1:</i> Seat group members at a table, with a sheet of paper in front of each person. At the top of the page, ask them to write down the problem that everyone is trying to solve. Appoint someone to be moderator, and time each round. ▪ <i>Step 2:</i> Give the group three minutes to write down three ideas for how to solve the problem. They should not edit the ideas. ▪ <i>Step 3:</i> After three minutes, move on to round two. Gather in the papers, shuffle them, and then pass them out. Ask everyone to generate three more ideas on the new paper received. ▪ <i>Step 4:</i> When all rounds are finished, collect the papers, and write all of the ideas on a whiteboard for everyone to see. Then begin discussing which ideas would work best for solving the current problem. 	

Tips

Remember to ask the participants not to write their names on the paper as the exercise should be anonymous. Do not allow any discussion while writing down. You may need to sort out cases where someone gets back a paper they have already written on. Allow people to write in any form or style. The moderator decides on how many rounds to implement.

Further reading

(Heslin 2009; Linsey and Becker 2010; Litcanu et al. 2015)

User Personas

Phase 1

Exploration & Inspiration

Activity 2

Define stakeholders and their needs

Materials

Issue cards, affinity diagram, character profiles

Description

This method is focused on using the everyday experiences of the users and their needs as a starting point when developing new products. This does not include real users but instead their representations. This leads to inclusion of the users' perspective in all aspects of the design process.

Goals

- Engage stakeholders (including citizens)
- Create new services
- Create new products
- Generate public values
- Transfer and sustainable conservation of implicit knowledge

Step-by-step

- *Step 1:* Find the users by profiling them.
- *Step 2:* Build hypotheses considering the characteristics of the users.
- *Step 3:* Verification. Find data to support the initial hypothesis.
- *Step 4:* Find patterns to make sense of the data collected.
- *Step 5:* Construct personas without stereotypes, but real users.
- *Step 6:* Define situations with real scenarios.
- *Step 7:* Validate and buy-in to collect the opinions of the participants.
- *Step 8:* Ongoing development with constantly updated information.

Tips

The information required can be gathered through interviews, observations, questionnaires, reports, companies and markets' data. The description of the user persona should include: a photo of the person, description of attitudes, the social background, emotions toward technologies and personal traits.

Further reading

(Browne, Temkin, and Geller 2008; Nielsen 2011)

Roadmapping

Phase 2

Ideation & concept design

Activity 1

Set your co-creation journey

Materials

Visual collaboration maps and mind maps, motivation matrix

Description

This method is focused on gathering and visualising insights of participants on which knowledge management processes may imply for the stakeholders and on how some knowledge indicators may be explained and used to increase their benefits. It also provides the pathways to achieve a desired state from a current state.

Goals

- Identify stakeholder needs
- Raise the level of awareness on different topics
- Generate public values
- Increase efficiency and effectiveness of services
- Provide financial and economical sustainability

Step-by-step

- *Step 1:* Establish goals to determine the purpose of your roadmap and who should be involved.
- *Step 2:* Gather inputs by collecting problems that need to be solved from stakeholders and existing research.
- *Step 3:* Create themes for clustering problems.
- *Step 4:* Prioritize themes by establishing criteria and a scoring framework to rank themes.
- *Step 5:* Visualize and share. Plot themes into a timeline and distribute the resulting visualization (your roadmap).
- *Step 6:* Revisit and update routinely to make adjustments as necessary.

Tips

Feel free to adapt your workshop or facilitation session to your needs and by choosing different tools. Establish a clear scope and define a set of responsibilities among the team. Start with a small set of participants and expand it when multiple rounds of interactions have been already implemented and you feel more comfortable with the approach.

Further reading

(Kazi, Hannus, and Zarli 2003)

Lego Serious Play

Phase 2

Ideation & concept design

Activity 2

Conceptualise & design

Materials

Issue cards, character profiles, affinity diagram

Description

It is a methodology aimed at identifying the positioning of a new service offer within a specific team. It enables to start a dialogue within a group on the potential exploitation of a service at early stages of development.

Goals

- Identify stakeholders needs
- Create new services
- Create new products
- Generate public values
- Support communities of practice
- Transfer and sustainable conservation of implicit knowledge
- Improve communication processes

Step-by-step

- *Step 1:* Posing a question or a challenge.
- *Step 2:* Building a personal model through the use of metaphors and story making.
- *Step 3:* Sharing the model with the other participants. This ensures 100% participation and 100% distribution and understanding of the knowledge.
- *Step 4:* Reflecting on the model to distil some insights, points of attention, clarifications in relation to the model.

Tips

Apply the methodology if you need a medium level of brainstorming by using metaphors. Explore any theme, but always consider three main sub-categories of analysis: development; integration; collaboration and communication. Inspire a learning by doing exercise and allow the audience to experience the LEGOs themselves without providing them any pre-filled information changing the end result.

Further reading

(Cantoni et al. 2009; Frick, Tardini, and Cantoni 2013; Gauntlett 2010; Mccusker 2014)

Basis SWOT Workshops

Phase 3

Planning & prototyping

Activity 1

Set the strategy

Materials

Toolkits, mock-ups, issue cards, motivation matrix

Description

This is a methodology used in bottom-up strategy development processes with different and heterogeneous stakeholder groups, especially in contexts involving regional or municipality strategy development. It helps to collect and visualise data that describe the actual situation of a group.

Goals

- Identify stakeholder needs and engage them
- Increase trust on governmental services
- Generate public values
- Increase efficiency and effectiveness of services
- Provide financial and economical sustainability of services

Step-by-step

- Step 1: Identify a homogeneous group and select the participants.
- Step 2: Prepare slides showing the different roles concerning knowledge transfer.
- Step 3: Provide an introduction about the context.
- Step 4: Describe the strategy development process.
- Step 5: Present the methodology and the agenda.
- Step 6: Collect strengths, weaknesses, opportunities and threats.
- Step 7: Select the most important SWOT categories.
- Step 8: Set the objectives for the innovation strategy.
- Step 9: Select and present actions to be implemented by voting them.

Tips

Describe the characteristics of the participants and their relation to the whole innovation system. Identify and present the role of the SWOT analysis inside the development process. Invite between 5 and 10 people maximum to the workshops for effective discussions and interactions towards results.

Further reading

(Barrett and van Gelder 2015; Wolf, Hauser, and Schweikert 2007)

Storyboard

Phase 3

Planning & prototyping

Activity 2

Prototype and develop

Materials

Mind mapping, post its, paper sheets, whiteboard

Description

The Storyboard is a graphical technique that helps you understand user tasks across a specific process of implementation. It includes pictures or drawings that focus on the user experience. Storyboards can be used to describe the current user experience as well as the desired one.

Goals

- Make better informed decisions by implementing a holistic approach to decision-making
- Identify problems before the development stage
- Evaluate and compare multiple ideas at once

Step-by-step

- *Step 1:* Define your focus, it can either be a problem or a set of ideas.
- *Step 2:* Plan the whole process for finding a solution and how the citizens would use your solution.
- *Step 3:* Create your journey into a paper sheet.
- *Step 4:* Share ideas among the participants and capture them on post-its.
- *Step 5:* Prioritise. Ask participants to vote for their favourite board.
- *Step 6:* Consolidate the best ideas and sections into a single storyboard.

Tips

Give people time to think individually about the idea and how an experience could work. Give each person a sheet of A4 white paper and fold it across and then three times vertically to create 6 boxes (or just draw them). Give each person a pen and ask them to draw out how they think the idea being considered should work. Enact a joint review to identify problems and clarify areas of confusion prior to development.

Further reading

(Haesen et al. 2010; van der Lelie 2006; Mohd Yusoff and Salim 2014; Mou, Jeng, and Chen 2013; Truong, Hayes, and Abowd 2006)

A/B Testing

Phase 4

Experimentation & evaluation

Activity 1

Test the solution

Materials

Online software tools

Description

A/B tests, also known as split tests, allow you to compare two versions of something to learn which is more effective. Simply put, do your users like version A or version B?. The concept is similar to the scientific method. If you want to find out what happens when you change one thing, you have to create a situation where only that one thing changes.

Goals

- Identify any changes required by the users to improve the solution.
- Evaluate the impact of changes that are relatively inexpensive to implement.
- Increase visits' rates.
- Reduce the lack of usability of digital solutions.
- Develop clear product images.

Step-by-step

- *Step 1:* Identify the problem in detail by asking why your solution is not successful.
- *Step 2:* Analyse user data. Focus on the specific target elements.
- *Step 3:* Develop a hypothesis to test. Narrow your unknowns down to determine how changing that element or elements might fix the problem you are facing.
- *Step 4:* Conduct the test.
- *Step 5:* Analyse the data to evaluate the changes.
- *Step 6:* Find new challengers for your champions and evaluate them against each other to define which is the best solution.

Tips

Define representative samples of your users. Make the groups equal in size and distributed according to gender, age, and geography. The more people you test, the more reliable your results will be. Let the test end before making changes. Run tests more than once for accurate results. You can always run another A/B test to evaluate the impact of another element, such as the size of the button or its colour scheme.

Further reading

(Andrasec et al. 2011; Kohavi and Longbotham 2017)

Appraisal interviews

<p>Phase 4</p> <p><i>Experimentation & evaluation</i></p> <p>Activity 2</p> <p><i>Evaluate societal impact</i></p> <p>Materials</p> <p>Visual collaboration maps and mind maps, toolkits</p>	<p>Description</p> <p>This method aims to evaluate past performances of an activity developed within a group and identify areas of further improvement. Usually it is exploited as a formal discussion process between an employee and his/her manager. This approach can be transferred through a reversed process among citizens and public bodies/industry.</p> <p>Goals</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Advance available services ▪ Increase efficiency of services ▪ Increase effectiveness of services ▪ Provide financial and economic sustainability
<p>Step-by-step</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ <i>Step 1:</i> Establish performance standards and criteria for evaluation. ▪ <i>Step 2:</i> Establish performance evaluation policies and the steps necessary for the process. ▪ <i>Step 3:</i> Prepare interview guidelines and evaluation criteria. ▪ <i>Step 4:</i> Schedule the interviews. ▪ <i>Step 5:</i> Conduct the face to face meeting by first introducing the topic, explaining the process, and setting the objectives of the discussion together. ▪ <i>Step 6:</i> Summarise the results, agree on the action plan and on milestones. 	
<p>Tips</p> <p>The activities developed by each actor within the organisation should be described. This approach allows us to identify the tasks that are more relevant for achieving the goals expected. It is crucial to evaluate the past activities carried out and to set the goals for the appraisal interview with a specific action plan. Share your view about the performance and discuss potential improvements. Find mutual agreements on the results of the performance assessment and delineate together the next steps to improve it.</p>	
<p>Further reading</p> <p>(Grote and Richard 1996; Nonaka and Takeuchi 1997; Probst, Raub, and Romhardt 2000)</p>	